

**STUDY OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES AND ANTIMICROBIAL
SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN IN BODY FLUIDS OF
PATIENTS FROM A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL**

**DISSERTATION FOR
MASTER OF SCIENCE
(MEDICAL MICROBIOLOGY)**

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(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY), KARAD**

**BY
MR. ROUNAK SHAKIL PATEL**

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

DR. SATYAJEET PAWAR

M.D., Ph.D.

Associate Professor

**DEPARTMENT OF MICROBIOLOGY
KRISHNA INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES KARAD-
415110, MAHARASHTRA.**

2023

**DEPARTMENT OF MICROBIOLOGY
KRISHNA INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES
KARAD - 415110**

DATE :

CERTIFICATE

Certified that the work embodied in the dissertation for the degree of **MSc in Medical Microbiology** at Krishna Vishwa Vidyapeeth (Deemed To Be University), Karad entitled “**Study of bacteria isolates and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in body fluids of patients from a tertiary care hospital**” was undertaken by **Mr. Rounak Shakil Patel** and was carried out in the Department of Microbiology, Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences, Karad, under my direct supervision and guidance to my satisfaction.

Dr. S. R. Patil (M.D, PhD)

Professor and Head,
Department of Microbiology,
KIMS, Karad

Dr. Satyajeet Pawar (M.D, PhD)

PG Guide and Associate Professor,
Department of Microbiology,
KIMS, Karad

Forwarded with compliment,

**Dr. Y. R. Kadam
DEAN
KIMS, Karad**

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Date: -

Place: - KVV, Karad

Mr. Rounak Shakil Patel

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ABBREVIATIONS

CSF	- Cerebrospinal fluid
MDR	- Multidrug-resistant
XDR	- Extensively drug-resistant
PDR	- Pandrug resistant
MRSA	- Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
VRE	- Vancomycin-resistant <i>Enterococcus</i>
ESBL	- Extended-spectrum β - lactamase
MBL	- Metallo-Beta Lactamase
AmpC	- Ampicillin class C - Beta Lactamase
CRE	- Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae
AST	- Antimicrobial susceptibility test
GNB	- Gram-negative bacilli
GPC	- Gram-positive cocci
COPS	- Coagulase-positive <i>Staphylococcus</i>
TSI	-Triple sugar iron
HCL	- hydrochloric acid
H₂O₂	- Hydrogen peroxide
CLSI	- Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute
μg	- Microgram
ml	- Millilitre

INTRODUCTION

Sterile body fluids are such fluids that do not contain any microbes and bacteria as commensals.¹ But when the bacteria can invade it and make it infected then such body fluid infections become life-threatening infection as a result of severe morbidity and mortality.²

Body fluids like cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), pleural fluid, pericardial, bile, peritoneal/ascitic fluid, synovial fluid, and drain are usually received samples in the microbiology laboratory for culture in suspected infections.³ Early detection and identification of organisms from infected body fluids and their antimicrobial susceptibility testing is important for the proper management of the patient. Prevalent bacterial growth is usually low in various body fluids because of a smaller number of pathogens and previous management by using empirical antibiotics in these patients.⁴ Even a single colony isolated from these specimens is considered a pathogenic microorganism.⁵

To complicate things further, many pathogens from body fluids are drug-resistant. Antimicrobial resistant organisms especially multidrug-resistant (MDR), extensively drug-resistant (XDR), pandrug-resistant (PDR), of their emergence and methicillin-resistant *staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and extended-spectrum β - lactamase (ESBL) producers are making it difficult in the patient's clinical management.⁴ Because of the practice of empirical treatment in resource-constrained settings, the prevalence of body fluid infection can become high.³ The literature on bacterial infection of body fluids and their antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in our area is very limited.² This study will be helpful for identifying the bacterial pathogens and their antimicrobial susceptibility testing in hospitalized patients in tertiary care hospitals.⁵ And this knowledge will help in early diagnosis, proper treatment and will help in preventing antibiotic resistance.⁶

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM:

To study the prevalence of bacterial infection and their antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in body fluids in a tertiary care hospital.

OBJECTIVES:

- 1) To study the prevalence of bacterial infection in various body fluids in the hospitalized patient.
- 2) To determine antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of the bacterial isolates

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. What is sterile body fluid: -

Body fluids are usually sterile because certain body sites or body regions in human body are considered as sterile because they do not contain bacteria and any microorganism as a commensal and sterile body fluids are such biological fluids where any kind of microorganisms cannot reside as a commensal or normal microbial flora.^{7,8,9}

2. Various sterile body fluids

Enlist of various sterile body fluids

- Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)
- Pericardial fluid
- Pleural fluid
- Peritoneal fluid/Ascitic fluid
- Synovial fluid^{3,6}

2.1. Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)

2.1.1. Define

Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) is a clear, colorless ultrafiltrate of plasma with low protein content and few cells. CSF is such a body fluid that is produced by the choroid plexus, which are the specialized secretory cells that are present centrally within the brain in the 3rd and 4th ventricles and ventricles are the cavities that contain fluid and such fluid is called as CSF.¹⁰

2.1.2. Location or site

Brain ventricles such as lateral ventricles and central 3rd ventricles and subarachnoid space of meninges (protective membranes of brain and spinal cord)¹¹

2.1.3. Synthesis or production

Choroid plexus are the specialized secretory cells that can produce CSF and these cells are situated in brain ventricles.¹⁰ CSF is about 150 ml, ventricles contain 25 ml and subarachnoid space contains 125 ml CSF.¹²

2.1.4. Chemical composition

CSF contains proteins and lipids.

- Proteins in CSF:-

Most of the studies on normal CSF have been done with fluids obtained by lumbar puncture. The total concentration of proteins in normal CSF is only about 0.4% of that present in plasma and rarely exceeds 2% even in diseases. The total protein content of normal CSF has been found to vary between 15 to 65 mg per 100 ml. High values are commonly observed in the new born and in old. During the first 3 months of life the total protein concentration of CSF appears to be even higher, reaching 120mg per ml.

- Lipids in CSF: -

The lipids content of normal lumbar fluid is extremely low being only about 1-2 mg% that the lipids of CSF are almost exclusively distributed.¹³ CSF is produced through ionic exchange and transport across both the basolateral and apical membranes of the choroid plexus epithelial cells. Briefly, the apical membrane $\text{Na}^+/\text{K}^+-\text{ATPase}$ is the primary active pump that not only provides the required energy for all other active exchanges needed for CSF secretion but also creates the electrochemical gradient for the import of Na^+ into the epithelial cells. The Na^+ influx occurs through the basolateral membrane Na^+/H exchanger (NHE1) as well as the Na^+ -dependent $\text{Cl}^-/\text{HCO}_3^-$ exchanger (NCBE). The HCO_3^- entry through the NCBE along with the cytoplasmic HCO_3^- production by the carbonic anhydrase enzyme increases the intracellular concentration of HCO_3^- . This in turn causes the transport of HCO_3^- from the epithelial cells to the blood through the basolateral $\text{Cl}^-/\text{HCO}_3^-$ anion exchanger (AE2) and to the ventricular lumen through the apical HCO_3^- channels. The entry of Cl^- into the epithelial cells via AE2 drives the efflux of Cl^- to the ventricular CSF through the apical $\text{Na}^+/\text{K}^+/\text{2Cl}^-$ co-transporter (NKCC1) as well as K^+/Cl^- co-transporter (KCC4). Apical membrane NKCC1 and KCC4 also export K^+ to the ventricles and therefore, contribute to the K

homeostasis of the CSF as a result, the newly synthesized CSF has a higher concentration of Na⁺, Cl⁻ and Mg²⁺, and a lower concentration of K⁺, Ca²⁺, glucose and protein as opposed to the plasma. The net flux of Na⁺, HCO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ from the blood to the ventricles generates the osmotic gradient that drives the transfer of water needed for CSF production. Water transport occurs through the highly permeable aquaporin-1 (AQP1) water channels that are expressed on both the basolateral and apical membranes. In addition, an alternative mechanism for water transport that is independent of the osmotic gradient has been suggested. It has been shown that approximately half of the CSF is produced via the co-transport of water along with ions through the apical NKCC1 channels. The water content in the CSF is 99% compared to 92% in the plasma.¹⁴

2.1.5. Function

Cerebrospinal fluid has four major functions: (1) physical support of neural structures, (2) excretion and "sink" action, (3) intracerebral transport, and (4) control of the chemical environment of the central nervous system. Cerebrospinal fluid provides a "water jacket" physical support and buoyancy. When suspended in CSF, a 1500-g brain weighs only about 50 g. The CSF is also protective because its volume changes reciprocally with changes in the volume of intracranial contents, particularly blood. Thus, the CSF protects the brain from changes in arterial and central venous pressure associated with posture, respiration, and exertion. Acute or chronic pathological changes in intra-cranial contents can also be accommodated, to a point, by changes in the CSF volume.

Excretory function is provided by the direct transfer of brain metabolites into the CSF. This capacity is particularly important because the brain lacks a lymphatic system. The lymphatic function of the CSF is also manifested in the removal of large proteins, and even cells such as bacteria or blood cells, by bulk CSF absorption. The "sink" action of the CSF arises from the restricted access of water-soluble substances to the CSF and the low concentration of these solutes in the CSF. Therefore, solutes entering the brain, as well as those synthesized by the brain, diffuse freely from the brain interstitial fluid into the CSF. Removal may then occur by bulk CSF absorption or, in some cases, by transport across the choroid plexus into the capillaries.

Because CSF bathes and irrigates the brain, including those regions known to participate in endocrine functions, CSF may serve as a vehicle for intracerebral transport of biologically active substances. For example, hormone-releasing factors, formed in the hypo thalamus and discharged into the CSF of the third ventricle, may be carried in the CSF to their effective sites in the median eminence. The CSF may also be the vehicle for intracerebral transport of opiates and other neuroactive substances.

An essential function of CSF is the provision and maintenance of an appropriate chemical environment for neural tissue. Anatomically, the interstitial fluid of the central nervous system and the CSF are in continuity; therefore, the chemical composition of the CSF reflects and affects the cellular environment. The composition of the CSF (and the interstitial fluid) is controlled by cells forming the interfaces, or barriers, between the "body" and the neural tissue. These semipermeable interfaces, the blood-brain barrier, the blood-CSF barrier, and the CSF-brain barrier, control the production and absorption of CSF and provide a fluid environment that is relatively stable despite changes in the composition of blood.¹⁵

2.1.6. Bacterial Causative agent

Streptococcus pneumoniae, *Niesseria meningitidis*, *Haemophiuls influenza*, *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Group B Strptococcus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Citrobacter koseri*, *Listeria monocytogenes*^{16,17}

2.1.7. Cerebrospinal fluid infection

The central nervous system (CNS) primarily consists of the brain and spinal cord, which are enclosed within the surrounding meninges and bone structures such as the calvarium and spine. Infectious diseases of the CNS include a wide spectrum of infections caused by various pathogens affecting one or more of these components as well as the spaces between these components. Different components or compartments of the CNS are affected circumstantially; each of the disease entities will have different imaging patterns and characteristics according to their different transmission routes, locations, and appearance, i.e. meningitis, brain abscess, septic emboli, spinal epidural empyema and osteomyelitis (OM). Despite the advances of modern medicine, accurate diagnoses of a specific disease entity of CNS infections have proven to be very challenging as

their clinical presentations are very general and nonspecific, such as fever, headaches, weakness, numbness, or back pain. Acute meningitis is an infection of the membranes (meninges) covering the brain and spinal cord. It is the most common infectious disease of the CNS. Either leptomeninges (pia and arachnoid matter) or pachymeninges (dura matter) can be affected. The leptomeningeal meningitis is more common than the pachymeningeal meningitis and is more conspicuous on neuroimaging.¹⁸

2.1.8. Clinical manifestation/signs & symptoms

Seizures, Problems with movement, balance, and coordination and Learning difficulties, Speech problems, Vision loss, Hearing loss.¹⁹

2.2. Pericardial Fluid

A pericardial effusion refers to the accumulation of excess fluid in the pericardial sac surrounding the heart. In a healthy individual, the pericardial sac contains between 15 and 50 milliliters (mL) of serous fluid. This fluid may be transudative, exudative, or sanguineous and may contain infectious organisms or malignant cells. It may be due to infection, inflammation, or direct filling of the pericardial sac by blood from a defect in the myocardium (iatrogenic or traumatic injury or cardiac wall rupture) or backfilling from an ascending aortic dissection that dissects into the pericardium. This activity examines when this condition should be considered on a differential diagnosis and how to properly evaluate for it and highlights the role of the interprofessional team in caring for patients with this condition.²⁰

2.2.1. Define

The pericardium is one of the serosal cavities of the mammals. It consists of two anatomical structures closely connected, an external sac of fibrous connective tissue, that is called fibrous pericardium and an internal that is called serous pericardium coating the internal surface of the fibrous pericardium (parietal layer) and the heart (visceral layer) forming the pericardial space and between these two layers a small amount of fluid exists that is called pericardial fluid.²¹

2.2.2 Location or site

Pericardium sac is the location of Pericardial fluid which contains 15 to 50 ml. serous fluid i.e., pericardial fluid. The pericardium is a double layered, fibro elastic sac

surrounding the heart. It consists of a visceral layer overlaying the pericardium, and a richly innervated parietal layer, separated by a potential space.²²

2.2.3. Synthesis or Production

Under normal conditions, the human pericardial cavity contains 20-60 ml of fluid. The pericardial fluid volume is determined by the equilibrium between production and drainage. There is strong evidence that the pericardial fluid is derived by plasma ultrafiltration through the epicardial capillaries (and probably the parietal's pericardium), as well as a small amount of interstitial fluid from the underlying myocardium, during the cardiac cycle. The fluid drainage is mainly accomplished through the parietal pericardium lymphatic capillary bed. Nevertheless, the whole procedure is not fully elucidated because of the difficulty to study pericardial fluid dynamics under normal conditions.²¹

2.2.4. Chemical composition

High levels of proteins, albumin and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), but not of glucose and cholesterol. High cellularity, mainly represented by mesothelial cells. Reference levels (Rls) for pericardial biochemistry were: protein content 1.7-4.6 g/dL PF/serum protein ratio 0.29-0.83, albumin 1.19-3.06 g/dL, pericardium-to- serum albumin gradient 0.18-2.37 g/dL, LDH 141– 2613 U/L, PF/serum LDH ratio 0.40-2.99, glucose 80- 134 mg/dL, total cholesterol 12-69 mg/dL, PF/serum cholesterol ratio 0.07-0.51. Rls for pericardial cells by optic microscopy were: 278-5608 x 10⁶ nucleated cells/L, 40-3790 x 10⁶ mesothelial cells/L, 35-2210 x 10⁶ leucocytes/L, 19-1634 x 10⁶ lymphocytes/L.^{22,23}

2.2.5. Function

The normal pericardium contributes in important functions. It is necessary for: Lubricating the moving surfaces of the heart, Stabilizing the heart anatomic position, Isolating the heart from the adjacent anatomical structures, prohibiting the adhesion formation, the inflammatory or neoplastic extension, limiting heart dilatation during diastole, reducing the endomyocardial tension, Preventing cardiac hypertrophy in pressure overload conditions, reducing the right ventricular impulse work in left ventricular over- load conditions. The ventriculoarterial blood retrogression prevention during high end-diastolic ventricular pressures, the preservation of the negative

endothoracic pressure, which is crucial for the venous blood filling, The nervous stimulation response and regulation of the cardiac frequency and arterial blood pressure, the formation of a hydrostatic compensation system ensuring that end-diastolic pressure remains the same at all hydrostatic levels and the Frank Starling mechanism is functional.

Many studies in both parietal and visceral pericardium (human, canine, pig) have shown the same mechanical properties, only with quantitative differences. In vitro studies in canine parietal pericardium demonstrated the presence of viscoelastic response, mainly attributed to the presence and the arrangement of the elastic and collagen fibers. These parietal pericardium properties are responsible for its participation to ventricular volume modulation, the intraventricular interaction, and the participation to the ventricular diastolic pressure/volume relationships In vitro epicardial studies (humans, pigs), proved the presence of elastic properties that have been attributed to the composition and orientation of the connective tissue. Specifically, the human epicardium undergoes an oblong and circumferential systolic shortening, thereby the energy gathering during the diastolic period may contribute to the passive mechanical properties of the myocardium. In this way, the epicardium seems to be participating in the ventricular end-diastolic volume control.²¹

2.2.6. Causative agent

Staphylococcus aureus and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* are the two most common pathogens causing bacterial pericarditis, although gram-negative bacilli and anaerobes are gaining more attention recently. *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, and *Legionella pneumophila* are rarely reported as the causes of bacterial pericarditis. Pericarditis due to *Borrelia burgdorferi* is less common than myocarditis. Oropharyngeal anaerobes (particularly *Actinomyces*, *Prevotella*, *Peptostreptococcus*, *Propionibacterium*, and *Fusobacterium*) play an important role in bacterial pericarditis in patients with complicated head and neck infections, either as a direct result of or seeding from the bloodstream to the pericardium. In children, *S. aureus* and *N. meningitidis* are the most common causes of bacterial pericarditis, whereas the incidence of pericarditis due to *Haemophilus influenzae* has been significantly reduced since the introduction of childhood immunization with the *H. influenzae* type B conjugate vaccine. In patients with HIV infection, *Mycobacterium*

tuberculosis, *Mycobacterium avium-intracellulare* (MAI), and *Mycobacterium kansasii* are responsible for up to 50% of the cases of pericarditis/pericardial effusion. On the other hand, 1%-5% of pericarditis in non- HIV-infected patients is caused by *M. tuberculosis*.²⁴

2.2.7. Infection of Pericardial fluid

Bacterial invasion in pericardial fluid leads to cause pericarditis. Pericarditis is inflammation in pericardial sac which lies on epicardium of the heart. Acute pericarditis is a common disorder caused by inflammation of the pericardium and can occur as an isolated entity or as a manifestation of an underlying systemic disease. It is diagnosed in approximately 0.1% of hospitalized patients and in 5% of patients admitted to the emergency department with noncardiac chest pain. In most patients, the cause of acute pericarditis is thought to be idiopathic because the yield of diagnostic tests to confirm etiology has been relatively low. Major known causes include viral and bacterial (e.g. tuberculous) microorganisms; systemic diseases, such as autoreactive or immune-mediated diseases; neoplastic invasion of the pericardium; uremia; previous acute myocardial infarction; aortic dissection and chest wall trauma; and previous cardiomy or thoracic surgery.²⁵

2.2.8. Clinical manifestation / signs and symptoms

Chest pain is the most common symptom of pericarditis. It usually feels sharp or stabbing. However, some people have dull, achy or pressure-like chest pain. Pericarditis pain usually occurs behind the breastbone or on the left side of the chest. The pain may: Spread to the left shoulder and neck, get worse when coughing, lying down or taking a deep breath, get better when sitting up or leaning forward, Other signs and symptoms of pericarditis may include: Cough, Fatigue or general feeling of weakness or being sick, Leg swelling, Low-grade fever, Pounding or racing heartbeat (heart palpitations), Shortness of breath when lying down, Swelling of the belly (abdomen). The specific symptoms depend on the type of pericarditis. Pericarditis is grouped into different categories, according to the pattern of symptoms and how long symptoms last.²¹

2.3. Pleural fluid

2.3.1 Define

Pleural effusion is a typical medical problem caused by fluid deposition in the pleural cavity. Increased pleural membrane permeability, decreased intrapleural negative pressure, increased pulmonary decreased oncotic pressure, capillary strain, obstructed lymphatic drainage and are all possible causes. Pleural effusion indicates the existence of a condition that may be coronary, pleural, or extrapulmonary. The pleural membrane is made of mesenchyme and lines the area between the lungs and the mediastinum, diaphragm, and chest wall throughout embryonic growth.²⁶

2.3.2 Location or site

Pleural fluid is produced at the parietal pleural level, mainly in the less dependent regions of the cavity. Reabsorption is accomplished by parietal pleural lymphatics in the most dependent part of the cavity, on the diaphragmatic surface and in the mediastinal regions. The pleural space contains a tiny amount (approximately 0.3 mL.kg⁻¹) of hypooncotic (low oncotic pressure) fluid (approximately 1 g.dL⁻¹ protein). Pleural fluid turnover is estimated to be approximately 0.15 mL.kg⁻¹.h⁻¹.²⁷

2.3.3. Synthesize or production

The pleural mesothelial cell is an essential cell in maintaining the normal homeostasis of the pleural space and it is also a central component of the pathophysiological processes affecting the pleural space.²⁸

Pleural fluid is produced at parietal pleural level, mainly in the less dependent regions of the cavity. Reabsorption is accomplished by parietal pleural lymphatics in the most dependent part of the cavity, on the diaphragmatic surface and in the mediastinal regions.²⁷ Pleural fluid is continuously produced by the parietal circulation in the way of bulk flow, while it is also continuously reabsorbed by the lymphatic system via the stomata in the parietal pleura. In a healthy human, the pleural space contains a small amount of fluid (about 10 to 20 mL), with a low protein concentration (less than 1.5 g/dL). Pleural fluid is filtered at the parietal pleural level from systemic microvessels to the extrapleural interstitium and into the pleural space down a pressure gradient. The lymphatics open as stomata directly onto the surface of the parietal pleura and provide

most (about 75%) of the drainage of the pleural cavity, while absorption through the visceral pleura is negligible. The visceral pleura does not account for any significant pleural fluid drainage under normal conditions. The rate of reabsorption can increase as a physiological response to accumulating pleural fluid or other fluid in the pleural space. The rate of absorption can increase roughly 40 times the reference rate before excess fluid begins to accumulate in the pleural space. Significant fluid accumulation in the pleural cavity usually indicates excess production of pleural fluid, lymphatic blockage, or some other source of fluid such as bleeding.²⁸

2.3.4. Chemical composition

The composition of normal pleural fluid consists of total white blood cell count of 1.716×10^3 cells/mL (-1). Differential cell counts: 75% macrophages, 23% lymphocytes, and marginally present mesothelial cells (1% to 2%), neutrophils (1%), and eosinophils (0%). Of note, there is a slight increase in the percent of neutrophils found in smokers over nonsmokers.²⁸

2.3.5. Function

The fluid functions as a lubricant to allow the two layers of the pleura to glide smoothly past each other during respiration. The pressure of the pleural fluid is sub-atmospheric and maintains the negative pressure between the lungs and thoracic cavity, which is necessary for inhalation while also preventing the lungs from collapsing.²⁸

The accumulation of pleural effusion has important effects on respiratory system function. It changes the elastic equilibrium volumes of the lung and chest wall, resulting in a restrictive ventilatory effect, chest wall expansion and reduced efficiency of the inspiratory muscles. The magnitude of these alterations depends on the pleural fluid volume and the underlying disease of the respiratory system. The decrease in lung volume is associated with hypoxemia mainly due to an increase in right to left shunt. The drainage of pleural fluid results in an increase in lung volume that is considerably less than the amount of aspirated fluid, while hypoxemia is not readily reversible upon fluid aspiration.²⁹

2.3.6. Causative agent

Streptococcus pneumoniae, *S. pyogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* are the organisms traditionally associated with pleural infection. Additionally, the *S. anginosus* group (often known as *S. milleri* group) consisting of *S. anginosus*, *S. constellatus* and *S. intermedius* are part of normal human flora which become significant in the context of pleural infection, accounting for 30-50% of adult cases of community acquired empyema.³⁰

2.3.7. Infection in pleural fluid

The morbidity and mortality rates in patients with pneumonia and associated pleural effusions are higher than for those in patients with pneumonia alone, with one study suggesting the increased relative risk for mortality was times higher. There also appears to be a rising incidence of pleural infection internationally. But despite continued advances in the management of this condition, morbidity and mortality have essentially remained static over the past decade. Historical perspective Infection of the pleural space is an ancient disease, with the earliest recorded description more than 5000 years ago and the first consistent description of its manifestations and treatment credited to the father of modern medicine, Hippocrates. Open thoracic drainage remained the standard treatment for pleural infection until the influenza pandemic of 1919; however, there was a 70% mortality rate associated with this treatment. In 1918 the U.S. Army Empyema Commission was formed to address the problem. They noted that dogs with empyema died more often if treated with early open drainage rather than delayed intervention, and the commission recommended using the closed-tube drainage techniques described by Hewitt and Bulau. The commission's summary recommendations were: adequate pus drainage with a closed tube, avoidance of early open drainage, obliteration of the pleural space, and proper nutritional support. A landmark paper by Graham charted the successes seen during this time, with short-term mortality plummeting to 4%. These treatment principles, described almost 100 years ago, remain essentially unchanged to this day. The discovery of penicillin in the 1940s was a major advance that led to a further reduction in mortality. Surgical techniques beyond open drainage were developed in the late 19th century, with thoracoplasty described by Estlander and Schede and with decortication described by Fowler and Beck. It was only recently, however, that video-assisted thoracic surgery (VATS) was

introduced and is being increasingly used today as the operation of choice in patients requiring surgery for their pleural infection.³¹

2.3.8. Clinical manifestation/signs and symptoms

The clinical presentation of pleural effusion depends on the amount of fluid present and the underlying cause. Many patients have no symptoms at the time a pleural effusion is discovered. Possible symptoms include pleuritic chest pain, dyspnea, and a dry, nonproductive cough. The chest pain associated with pleural effusion is caused by pleural inflammation of the parietal pleura resulting from movement-related friction between the two pleural surfaces. Pleuritic chest pain may be localized or referred.³²

2.4. Peritoneal fluid / Ascitic fluid

2.4.1. Define

Ascites is the accumulation of fluid within the peritoneal cavity.³⁵ There is a cavity which lies on abdominal visceral organs, such cavity is called as peritoneal cavity which contains a serous fluid known as peritoneal fluid.³⁴

2.4.2. Location or sites

The peritoneum is a single layer of squamous mesothelial cells resting on a loose connective tissue containing blood vessels, lymphatics, and nerves. Anatomically, the peritoneum is divided into a parietal and visceral peritoneum. The parietal peritoneum lines the diaphragm, abdominal walls, and pelvic cavity. The parietal peritoneum is continuous with the visceral peritoneum, which encloses the intraperitoneal organs and forms the omentum and mesenteries of the abdominal cavities. A small volume of peritoneal fluid lubricates the surface of the visceral and parietal peritoneum. together the peritoneum and fluid are responsible for preventing adhesion formation.³⁵

2.4.3. Synthesis or production

The peritoneal cavity of the human usually contains 5 - 20 ml of serous exudate which varies widely depending on the physiological condition. In the female, this volume changes during the menstrual cycle to reach maximal levels after ovulation. When pressure in the hepatic sinusoids rises more than 5 to 10 mm Hg, fluid containing large amounts of protein transudes through the liver surface into the abdominal cavity. Excess

fluid in the peritoneal cavity is either a transudate (specific gravity < 1.010), which accumulates (ascites) from peritoneal obstruction or circulatory differences (failure, portal cardiac hypertension, hypofibrinogenemia, etc.), or an exudate (specific gravity > 1.020), which arises from inflammation. The hepatic resistance to portal blood flow induces a capillary pressure in the visceral peritoneum that is higher than elsewhere in the body. The pH of peritoneal fluid ranges between 7.5 and 8.0 and contains significant buffering capacity. The pH of peritoneal fluid in aspirates from 59 patients with perforated peptic ulcer was 7.0 to 7.8. Due to the hydrostatic pressure gradient between plasma and the peritoneal compartment, normal peritoneal fluid also contains many of the plasma proteins in about 50% of the plasma concentration.³⁶

2.4.4. Chemical composition

Peritoneal fluid is produced by transudation from sub mesothelial vessels across the peritoneal membrane. The amount of fluid is normally small (less than 50 mL in humans) and contains neutrophils, mononuclear cells, eosinophils, macrophages, lymphocytes, desquamated mesothelial cells, and an average of 3.0 g/mL of protein. The volume often increases during late pregnancy.³⁷

2.4.5. Function

Peritoneal fluid formation is a dynamic process that is maintained in a delicate equilibrium. It is dependent on factors of production, absorption, and the integrity of the peritoneal membrane and lymphatic drainage system. There is a constant exchange of fluid and proteins between the plasma and peritoneal cavity, and this fluid equilibrium is controlled by osmotic and hydrostatic pressures within the hepatic and mesenteric capillaries. Under the influence of these pressures, 40% to 80% of intraperitoneal fluid is exchanged with the plasma every hour. The lymphatic system is responsible for the removal of interstitial fluid. Ascites arises when the net transfer of fluid from the peritoneal capillary bed (hepatic and mesenteric capillaries) to the peritoneal cavity occurs at a rate that overcomes the drainage capacity of the lymphatics, leading to accumulation of peritoneal fluid. Factors that regulate lymph flow include oncotic pressure, hydrostatic pressure, and possibly nitric oxide, which modulates smooth muscle contractility. In adults, 800 to 1000 mL of lymph is produced a day, with the majority of lymph being produced from abdominal viscera.³³

2.4.6. Causative agent

Traditionally, three fourths of spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) infections have been caused by aerobic gram-negative organisms (50% of these being *Escherichia coli*). The remainder has been due to aerobic gram-positive organisms (19% *Streptococcal species*). Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*.³⁸

2.4.7. Infection in peritoneal fluid

Hepatic Cirrhosis: - Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) is, as the name implies, the sudden and unprovoked development of peritoneal fluid infection in a cirrhotic patient.³⁹

Ascites and Hyponatremia: - Ascites is the pathologic accumulation of fluid in the peritoneal cavity, and its most common cause is cirrhosis. That fluid accumulates in the abdominal cavity has been known since ancient times, and it was Hippocrates who recognized that ascites (from the Greek askos, meaning a leather bag used to carry wine, water, or oil) derived from a diseased liver carried a grim prognosis. The development of ascites is one of the complications of cirrhosis that marks the transition from compensated to decompensated cirrhosis. Other complications that mark this transition are variceal hemorrhage, hepatic encephalopathy, and jaundice; however, ascites is the most common first decompensating event in patients with cirrhosis.⁴⁰

Peritonitis: - is an inflammation of the parietal and visceral peritoneum, usually occurring in association with another pathologic process. When localized, peritonitis is characterized by the formation of an intra-abdominal abscess. While deaths from peritonitis have declined dramatically with the advent of broad-spectrum antibiotics and modern pre- and postoperative, it remains a potentially fatal disease.⁴¹

2.4.8. Clinical manifestation

Swelling in the abdomen, Weight gain, Sense of fullness, Bloating, Sense of heaviness, Nausea or indigestion, Vomiting, Swelling in the lower legs, Shortness of breath, Hemorrhoids.⁴²

2.5. Synovial fluid

Synovial fluid (SF) is normally a clear, straw-colored and viscous liquid. The molecular and cellular constituents within SF give rise to its unique properties and functions in maintaining joint homeostasis.⁴⁴

2.5.1. Define

Synovial fluid is defined as the collection of fluid confined within a joint space. Synovial fluid is produced by the synovium and coats the tendons in the tendon sheaths and the surface of the synovium in normal joints. Synovial fluid is cleared through the subintimal lymphatic vessels which are assisted by joint motion. Synovial fluid is essential for the nutrition and lubrication of articular cartilage and tendons. It is composed of plasma ultrafiltrate, which diffuses in the joint space from the subintimal vasculature, and hyaluronic acid and lubricin secreted by the fibroblast-derived type B synoviocytes.^{44,45}

2.5.2. Location or site

Synovial fluid is the viscous fluid liquid in the synovial cavity.⁴⁶ synovial fluid is defined as the collection of fluid confined within a joint space.⁴⁷

2.5.3. Synthesize and production

Synovial fluid is produced by the synovium and coats the tendons in the tendon sheaths and the surface of the synovium in normal joints. Synovial fluid is cleared through the subintimal lymphatic vessels which are assisted by joint motion. Synovial fluid is essential for the nutrition and lubrication of articular cartilage and tendons. It is composed of plasma ultrafiltrate, which diffuses in the joint space from the subintimal vasculature, and hyaluronic acid and lubricin secreted by the fibroblast-derived type B synoviocytes. Hyaluronan is the major component of synovial fluid and is important in maintaining synovial fluid viscosity and prevents fluid loss from the articular cavity. Lubricin is present at the articular cartilage interface and is essential for joint lubrication and maintenance of a healthy joint. The concentrations of small molecules and electrolytes in the synovial fluid mirror those in plasma, while the concentration of large molecules is inversely proportional to their molecular weight.⁴⁸

2.5.4. Chemical composition

The main components of SF are water, hyaluronic acid (HA; roughly 3–4 mg/mL), d-glucuronic acid, d-N-acetylglucosamine, growth hormone prolactin, and lubricin. Because SF is the fluid covering the tissues of the joint, it is closer to the cartilage and synovial membrane than blood.⁴⁹

2.5.5. Function

Synovial fluid (SF), present in very small quantities in normal synovial joints, has two functions: lubrication and nutrition. Normal fluid is clear and pale yellow; SF is a combination of a filtrate of plasma, which enters the joint space from the sub synovial capillaries, and hyaluronic acid, which is secreted by the synoviocytes. Hyaluronic acid provides the high viscosity of normal SF and, with water, its lubricating properties. Concentrations of small molecules (electrolytes, glucose) are similar to those in plasma, but larger molecules (e.g., complement components) are present in low concentrations relative to plasma unless an inflammatory state alters vascular permeability. Notably absent from SF are elements of the coagulation pathway (fibrinogen, prothrombin, factors V and VII, tissue thromboplastin, and antithrombin). As a result, normal SF is resistant to clotting. There appears to be free exchange of small molecules between SF of the joint space and water bound to collagen and proteoglycan of cartilage.⁵⁰

2.5.6. Causative agent

The most common bacterial isolates in native joints include gram-positive cocci, primarily with *Staphylococcus aureus* (60%). Other isolates include *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (in sexually active young adults), *Streptococci*, and gram-negative cocci. Other organisms less commonly isolated include *Mycobacteria* and fungi. Gram-negative bacilli are often present in neonates, older adults, and patients with immune deficiency disorders.⁵¹

2.5.7. Infection in synovial fluid and clinical form

An infection of native joints leads generally to suppurative arthritis, which may be of one joint (monoarticular) or several joints (oligoarticular). Bacteria that produce symptoms in multiple joints during bacteremia, such as *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, may also induce inflammation in the neighboring tendon sheaths. Viral infections frequently

involve multiple joints and produce inflammation without suppuration. Chronic granulomatous monoarticular arthritis may occur because of infection with either mycobacteria or fungi, which must be differentiated from other causes of chronic monoarticular arthritis. A sterile arthritis may occur early in infection (as with hepatitis B), or later (as with a post-infectious arthritis). Any patient presenting with an inflamed joint should have infection as a diagnostic possibility and appropriate cultures must be performed.⁵¹

2.5.8. Clinical manifestation

Joint pain, swelling at the site, deformity. CT or x-ray may show erosive changes.⁵²

2.6. Bile

Bile is a fluid that is made and released by the liver and stored in the gallbladder.⁵³

2.6.1. Define

Bile is the fluid which is secreted by the liver, it is a complex fluid containing H₂O, electrolytes, and several organic molecules including bile acids, cholesterol, phospholipids, and bilirubin that flow through the biliary tract into the small intestine.⁵⁴

2.6.2. Location or site

Bile is the digestive fluid produced and secreted by the liver, is transported by a series of branching bile ducts known collectively as the biliary tree. At the cellular level, several narrow tubular channels called canaliculi collect the bile generated by each hepatocyte.⁵⁵

2.6.3. Synthesis and production

Bile fluid is produced by hepatocytes and it is then modified by the cholangiocytes lining the bile ducts. The production and secretion of bile require active transport systems within hepatocytes and cholangiocytes in addition to a structurally and functionally intact biliary tree. Initially, hepatocytes produce bile by secreting conjugated bilirubin, bile salts, cholesterol, phospholipids, proteins, ions, and water into their canaliculi (thin tubules between adjacent hepatocytes that eventually join to form bile ducts). The canalicular membrane of the hepatocyte is the main bile secretory

apparatus that contains the intracellular organelles, the cytoskeleton of the hepatocyte, and carrier proteins.

The carrier proteins in the canalicular membrane transport bile acid and ions. Transporter proteins found within the canalicular membrane use energy to secrete molecules into bile against concentration gradients. Through this active transport, osmotic and electrochemical gradients are formed. When conjugated bile salts enter the canaliculus, water follows by osmosis. The electrochemical gradient allows for the passive diffusion of inorganic ions such as sodium. The most significant promoter of bile formation is the passage of conjugated bile salts into the biliary canaliculus. The total bile flow in a day is approximately 600 ml, of which 75% is derived from hepatocytes, and 25% is from cholangiocytes.⁵⁶

2.6.4. Chemical composition

The inorganic solutes (sodium, potassium, calcium, and bicarbonate) have a concentration in bile that is similar to plasma and account for the bile osmolality of approximately 300 mOsm/kg. The major organic solutes are bile acids, bilirubin, cholesterol, and phospholipids.⁵⁷

2.6.5. Function

Bile secretion is one of the major functions of the liver, and it serves two major purposes: 1) the excretion of hepatic metabolites—including bilirubin, cholesterol, drugs, and toxins—and 2) the facilitation of intestinal absorption of lipids and fat-soluble vitamins. Alterations in bile secretion may contribute to cholelithiasis and its potential complications, such as cholecystitis and choledocholithiasis. On the other hand, obstruction of bile flow results in alterations of coagulation, the immune system, and all organ function. This chapter will discuss the physiology of bile secretion, the pathophysiology of bile obstruction, and the management of obstructive jaundice.⁵⁸

2.6.6. Causative agent

Escherichia coli, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Enterococcus faecium*.⁵⁹

2.6.7. Infection in the bile and clinical form

Biliary tract infections are encountered frequently in gastrointestinal (GI) practice. Cholangitis is a clinical syndrome comprising fever, pain, and jaundice. Obstruction and stasis in the biliary tract leads to raised intrabiliary pressure, which subsequently results in bacteremia.⁶⁰

2.6.8. Clinical manifestation

Anorexia, Vomiting, Icterus, Abdominal pain, Serum biochemical abnormalities such as increased serum ALT, ALP, and serum bilirubin.⁶¹

2.7. Vitreous fluid

Vitreous humor is the fluid-like gel, composed of approximately 98–99% water with trace amounts of hyaluronic acid, glucose, anions, cations, ions, and collagen, located in the posterior chambers of the eyes.⁶²

2.7.1. Define

Vitreous humor (VH) is a gel-like fluid obtained from the eye. Because it is in an isolated compartment well removed from the gut, putrefaction usually starts much later in the VH than it does in blood. Metabolism of alcohol in the VH is also minimal. For these reasons, the VH is often analyzed for alcohol when decomposition of the blood is suspected. If alcohol is found in VH, it may be used as evidence of antemortem alcohol consumption.⁶³

2.7.2. Location or site

The vitreous humor is the fluid located behind the lens of the eye. As the vitreous humor is isolated by membranes from the remainder of the decomposing body, attempts have been made to use the chemistry of the fluid to estimate the postmortem interval.⁶⁴

2.7.3. Synthesize or production

Vitreous fluid is Produced by cells in the non-pigmented portion of the ciliary body, the vitreous humor is derived from embryonic mesenchyme cells, which degenerate after birth.⁶⁵

2.7.4. Chemical composition

Vitreous humor is the fluid-like gel, composed of approximately 98–99% water with trace amounts of hyaluronic acid, glucose, anions, cations, ions, and collagen, located in the posterior chambers of the eyes. The relatively simple composition of vitreous humor allows it to be analyzed by methods that require little, if any, sample preparation.⁶⁶

2.7.5. Function

Previously vitreous fluid was considered that the vitreous body had no well-substantiated physiological function, apart from giving the eye its shape and volume, so that the eye would not be adversely affected by vitreous gel removal.^{67,68}

However, the new studies about vitreous found that an intact vitreous gel is crucial for stable intraocular metabolism and function. The vitreous gel plays a major role in refraction, cellular barriers, participating in intraocular oxygen metabolism and the pathology of diseases. To understand the physiological function of the vitreous body, we must first understand its structure, components, development, and metabolism.

The transparent, gelatinous vitreous makes up 80% of the intraocular volume, adjacent to the retina, lens and ciliary body. The vitreous gel is composed of the vitreous membrane, cortex and nucleus. The vitreous membrane, composed of dense collagen fibers, is located in the peripheral part of the vitreous. The vitreous cortex is located between the vitreous membrane and nucleus. The vitreous nucleus occupies most of the space in the middle, and in the center is the Cloquet canal, degenerated from the vascular primary vitreous with aging. The vitreous is most closely connected with the retina at the vitreous base, macula and optic disc. The posterior vitreous boundary membrane and inner limiting membrane jointly constitute the vitreous-retina interface.

As the embryo develops, vitreous gel formation is a dynamic process in which the avascular transparent secondary vitreous gradually replaces the primary vitreous. The highly hydrated, almost acellular vitreous gel is composed mainly of collagen and hyaluronan, with water accounting for approximately 98%-99% of it. The vitreous gel consists of only 0.1% macromolecules, in which collagens might be the most important for the structure of the vitreous gel.^{68,69,70,71,72,73}

2.7.6. Causative agent

*Pseudomonas spp. Staphylococcus epidermidis, Bacillus cereus, Streptococcus spp. Staphylococcus aureus, Enterobacter spp. Acinetobacter spp. Klebsiella spp. Citrobacter spp. Streptococcus pneumoniae, Nocardia spp.*⁷⁴

2.7.7. Infection in vitreous fluid and clinical form

Endophthalmitis means bacterial or fungal infection inside the eye, involving the vitreous and/or aqueous humors. Most cases of endophthalmitis are exogenous, and organisms are introduced into the eye via trauma, surgery, or an infected cornea. Endogenous endophthalmitis occurs when the eye is seeded via the bloodstream. Patients usually have symptoms from their underlying systemic infection, but sometimes present only with eye symptoms.

Endophthalmitis does not serve as a source of bacteremia or fungaemia. Infection remains confined to the eye. In panophthalmitis, infection spreads from the globe of the eye to the adjacent soft tissues of the orbit.

Most cases of endophthalmitis present acutely, with hours to a few days of symptoms. These cases are medical emergencies, as delay in treatment may result in permanent vision loss.⁷⁵

2.7.8. Clinical manifestations

Symptoms are classically a sudden onset of flashes of light, due to tugging on the vitreoretinal adhesion, and floaters. If the vitreous detaches from the optic nerve head, it can be seen as a ring-like vitreous floater or Weiss ring. The flashes of light are commonly reported as lightning streaks in peripheral vision. Retinal tears are associated with about 8% of cases of symptomatic PVD and must be investigated. They typically lead to symptoms of a shower of small floaters and signs of pigment granules (from the RPE) in the anterior vitreous, vitreous hemorrhage and the tear itself.⁷⁶

3. Various bacterial infection in sterile body fluid

A wide range of various bacterial agents have been described as sterile body fluid infections including Gram positive such as - *Staphylococcus spp. Streptococcus spp.*

Micrococcus spp. Enterococci spp. And as well as Gram negative bacteria such as – Neisseria spp. Acinetobacter spp. Escherichia spp. Enterobacter spp. Proteus spp.^{77,78}

3.1. Gram positive bacteria

Gram-positive bacteria are characterized by their thick walls, which are composed of peptidoglycans and mucocomplexes containing muramic acid and stain prominently with osmium as 20- to 50-nm thick, electron-dense layers surrounding the plasma membrane. Gram positivity is due to the thick peptidoglycan layer, which gives shape, strength, and rigidity to the cell wall. An ultrastructural Gram technique replaces the crystal violet–iodide complex with a complex platinum salt–containing compound.⁷⁹

Gram-positive bacteria lack an outer membrane but proteins, lipoproteins and other macromolecules are associated with the cytoplasmic membrane and peptidoglycan.⁸⁰

Gram-positive bacteria and, in general, monoderms have complex envelopes comprising one bilayer lipid membrane separating the cytoplasm from the exterior of the cell. The membrane is part of a very complex structure that comprises many layers up to 40 in the case of murein, or peptidoglycan, a complex of peptides containing d-amino acids in particular mesodiaminopimelic acid, and amino sugars. The cell envelope also has several layers of teichoic acid.⁸¹

3.1.1. Gram positive cocci

Gram-positive cocci approximately 1 µm in diameter occur as pairs or chains depending on the culture environment: usually as pairs (diplococci) in the animal but as elongated chains in vitro; diplococci are more virulent.⁸²

Gram-positive cocci such as *Streptococcus spp.*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, are the most frequently associated organisms.⁸³

3.1.1.1. Genus *Staphylococcus*

The genus *Staphylococcus* covers a large group of Gram-positive bacteria that are classified taxonomically in the family Staphylococcaceae, order Bacillales, class Bacilli, phylum Firmicutes. Representing one of the five genera i.e. *Jeotgalicoccus*, *Macrococcus*, *Nosocomiicoccus*, *Salinicoccus* and *Staphylococcus*). Within the family Staphylococcaceae, the genus *Staphylococcus* is complex and contains more than 40

recognized species such as *S. aureus*, *S. auricularis*, *S. capitis*, *S. caprae*, *S. cohnii*, *S. condimenti*, *S. delphini*, *S. epidermidis*, *S. felis*, *S. fleurettii*, *S. gallinarum*, *S. haemolyticus*, *S. hominis*, *S. hyicus*, *S. intermedius*, *S. kloosii*, *S. leei*, *S. lentus*, *S. lugdunensis*, *S. lutrae*, *S. microti*, *S. muscae*, *S. pasteurii*, *S. pseudintermedius*, *S. pseudolugdunensis*, *S. pulvereri*, *S. rostri*, *S. saprophyticus*, *S. warneri*, etc. with some *Staphylococcus spp.* being further divided into subspecies with analyses of the 16S rRNA sequences have enabled the separation of *Staphylococcus spp.* into 11 clusters.⁸⁴

3.1.1.2. Genus *Streptococcus*

Streptococci are spherical organisms that grow in chains because of incomplete separation after division of the cells. They were first described in 1874 by Billroth, who used the term 'Streptococcus' (from two Greek words: streptos means chain, kokkos means berry). In the beginning, streptococci were classified according to the disease they caused; however, thanks to advances in diagnostics, and with the availability of modern molecular techniques, many changes have been made in the taxonomy of the *Streptococcus* genus in the last decade. Historically, a useful identifying characteristic of streptococci has been the reaction they show on blood agar, caused by the lysis of erythrocytes by enzymes released by the *Streptococcus* – a phenomenon known as hemolysis. Based on this characteristic, streptococci were classified into β -hemolytic and non- β -hemolytic groups. In 1934, streptococci were further classified based on the presence of group-specific polysaccharides on the bacterial surface. In this serogrouping, mostly β -hemolytic streptococci were considered. Thirteen different serological groups have so far been identified, out of which groups A, B, C, and G, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *viridans group streptococci* are most important with regards to human health.⁸⁵

3.1.1.3. Genus *Micrococcus*

Micrococcus spp. are Gram-positive aerobic spherical cocci. They are catalase positive, reduce nitrate to nitrite and are usually non-motile.⁸⁶

Micrococcus are found in soils and fresh water, and frequently on the skin of humans and other animals. There are currently 10 species of *Micrococcus* on the list of prokaryotic names with standing in nomenclature *M. agilis*; *M. antarcticus*; *M. halobius*; *M. kristinae*; *M. luteus*; *M. lylae*; *M. nishinomiyaensis*; *M. roseus*; *M.*

sedentarius; *M. varians*.⁸⁷ Micrococcus rarely found in sterile body fluid as compared to other pathogens.

3.1.1.4. Genus Enterococcus

Enterococcus spp. are Gram-positive, catalase negative, non-spore-forming bacteria, which can appear either as single cocci or as pairs, chains or clusters. The term Enterococcus was first described by Thiercelin in 1899, when he described intestinal commensal bacteria with the ability to become pathogenic. This genus consists of 58 described species. It belongs to the family Enterococcaceae which is in the order Lactobacillales, class Bacilli in the phylum Firmicutes.⁸⁸

3.2. Gram negative organisms

Gram-negative bacteria have a cell envelope containing two membranes, the outer membrane is characterized by the presence of lipopolysaccharide in the outer leaflet of the bilayer structure. The lipopolysaccharide is involved in several aspects of pathogenicity.⁸⁹

3.2.1. Gram negative cocci

Gram-negative bacteria possess a number of cell surface glycans that have been shown to play an important role in the biosynthesis and regulation of the cell wall of pathogenic Gram-negative bacteria.⁹⁰ Gram-negative cocci are almost invariably isolated from nasopharyngeal cultures of human beings. The majority of these are commensal species. Members of the genus *Neisseria* are nonmotile and oxidase- and catalase-positive Gram-negative diplococci that utilize sugars oxidatively.⁹¹

3.2.1.1. Genus *Neisseria*

Neisseria spp. are a Gram-negative non-spore-forming diplococcus that has a flattened shape; its size ranges between 0.6–0.8 µm. They are oxidase-positive, non-acid-fast cocci or plump rods. They can reach a diameter of around 0.6–0.8 µm and sometimes up to 1.0 × 2.0–3.0 µm.⁹²

Neisseria sp. such as *N. meningitidis* and *N. gonorrhoeae* infects human cells by interaction with cellular barriers. These pathogens highly infect several types of cells including blood, plasma, epithelial, and endothelial cells.⁹³

3.2.2. Gram Negative Coccobacilli

3.2.2.1. *Haemophilus influenzae*

Haemophilus influenzae is a gram-negative coccobacillus that represents a common cause of both localized respiratory tract and systemic bacteremia in humans. Non-capsulated, non-typable strains account for the majority of *H. influenzae* respiratory tract disease, whereas encapsulated, serotype b strains are responsible for most cases of *H. influenzae* systemic disease.⁹⁴

Haemophilus influenzae is among the most common causes of bacterial meningitis and other invasive infections in infants and young children throughout the world.⁹⁵

3.2.2.2. *B. pertussis*

Bordetella pertussis is the agent of whooping cough, a highly contagious respiratory disease, dramatic for infants and also for elderly and pregnant women. This bacterium secretes adhesins and toxins acting in synergy to cause local and systemic cytopathogenic effects observed during the disease.⁹⁶ *Bordetella pertussis* rarely found in sterile body fluid as compared to other pathogens.

3.2.3. Gram negative bacilli

Gram-negative bacteria (GNB) are among the world's most significant public health problems due to their high resistance to antibiotics.⁹⁷

Gram-negative bacteria have a cell envelope containing two membranes, the outer membrane is characterized by the presence of lipopolysaccharide in the outer leaflet of the bilayer structure. The lipopolysaccharide is involved in several aspects of pathogenicity. It serves as the hydrophobic anchor of Gram-negative bacteria. Lipopolysaccharide is a complex polymer of four parts.⁹⁸

3.2.3.1 Genus *pseudomonas*

The genus *Pseudomonas* contains more than 140 species, most of which are saprophytic. Over 25 species are associated with human infections. Bacteria from the family Pseudomonadaceae are strictly aerobic, Gram-negative rods with polar flagella that provide motility¹⁰⁰

The genus *Burkholderia* represents the RNA group II of Pseudomonadaceae and possesses other and significant structural features in its LPS core regions which are of chemotaxonomic value.^{111,112}

3.2.3.2. Genus *Acinetobacter*

The genus *Acinetobacter* (coming from the Greek “akinetos,” meaning non-motile) was proposed by Brisou and Prevot.^{113,114} The genus *Acinetobacter* was widely accepted by 1968 after Baumann et al.¹¹⁵

Acinetobacter spp. are Gram-negative coccoid rods that are sometimes difficult to destain.¹¹⁶ *Acinetobacter* is a gram-negative bacterium that typically appears as a rod 0.9 to 1.6 µm in diameter and 1.5 to 2.5 µm in length, but it may become spherical in the stationary phase of growth.¹¹⁷

3.2.3.3. Genus *Escherichia*

The genus *Escherichia* derives its name from Theodor Escherich, who first isolated this organism from feces in 1885 and it comes under the family of Gram-negative bacteria i.e., Enterobacteriaceae.^{118,119}

The Gram-negative genus *Escherichia* is composed of five species: *E. albetii*, *E. coli*, *E. fergusonii*, *E. hermanii* and *E. vulneris*, with *E. coli* as the type-species. Based on its surface antigens (i.e. somatic O antigen, flagellar H antigen, and capsular K antigen), *E. coli* is differentiated into >190 serogroups (serotypes). Consequently, an *E. coli* isolate may be referred by its specific combination of O and H antigens (e.g. O157:H7).¹²⁰

3.2.3.4. Genus *Klebsiella*

Members of this genus are VP (Voges–Proskauer) test positive. The *Klebsiella spp.* produce abundant amount of CO₂ in KIA (Kligler Iron Agar) and TSI (Triple Sugar Iron) slants and are nonmotile. The important members of the genus *Klebsiella* associated with infections are *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Klebsiella oxytoca*. They are found as saprophyte in soil and water and as commensals in human intestine. They are one of the leading species responsible for nosocomial infections like ventilator associated pneumonia and catheter associated UTI.^{121,122} The four recognized species

include *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Klebsiella terrigena*, and *Klebsiella planticola*. *K. pneumoniae*, the most common human pathogen.¹²³

Klebsiella is a gram-negative, anaerobic bacterium, which under the microscope is shaped like a rod. It belongs to the family Enterobacteriaceae and is a normal commensal living in the mouth and gut. However, when *Klebsiella* becomes transported elsewhere it becomes pathogenic.¹²⁴

3.2.3.5. Genus *Enterobacter*

Enterobacter is the genus within the family Enterobacteriaceae.¹²⁵ The genus *Enterobacter* was first proposed by Hormaeche and Edwards in 1960 when the motile and ornithine decarboxylase (ODC) positive members of the genus *Aerobacter* were separated out as *Enterobacter* in order to distinguish them from the nonmotile and ODC negative *Klebsiella* strains.¹²⁶

3.2.3.6. Genus *Proteus*

The genus *Proteus* belongs to the tribe Proteeae of family Enterobacteriaceae and includes five species: *Proteus vulgaris*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Proteus penneri*, *Proteus myxofaciens*, and *Proteus hauseri*. Besides these, there are three unnamed *Proteus* genomospecies.¹²⁷

Proteus syndrome consists of disproportionate or segmental overgrowth of limbs and macrocephaly associated with cranial hyperostoses, plantar hyperplasia; hemangiomas, lipomas or lymphangiomas, verrucous epidermal nevi, and variable psychomotor deficiency.¹²⁸

4. Risk factor for Bacterial infection

Bacteria are one of the prokaryotes and ubiquitous in nature. They play an important role in maintaining the environment in which we live. Several factors lead to the development of bacterial infection and disease. First, the infectivity of an organism determines the number of individuals that will be infected compared to the number who are susceptible and exposed. Second, the pathogenicity is a measure of the potential for an infectious organism to cause disease. Pathogenic bacteria possess characteristics that allow them to evade the body's protective mechanisms and use its resources, causing disease. Finally, virulence describes the organism's propensity to cause disease, through

properties such as invasiveness and the production of toxins. Host factors are critical in determining whether disease will develop following transmission of a bacterial agent. These factors include genetic makeup, nutritional status, age, duration of exposure to the organism, and coexisting illnesses. The environment also plays a role in host susceptibility. Air pollution as well as chemicals and contaminants in the environment weaken the body's defenses against bacterial infection.¹²⁹

5. Bacterial Pathogenesis

The human body harbors a large number of bacteria but their localization in healthy individuals is normally restricted to certain body areas such as the skin, the mucosae of buccal and nasal cavities, vagina and, most importantly, the gastrointestinal tract.^{130,131,132} The internal tissues are normally sterile. In some circumstances, however, some opportunistic pathogens are able to enter the host by taking advantage of injuries or breaches in one of the different host barriers. In addition, bona fide pathogens have evolved mechanisms to cross host barriers and reach deeper organs where they proliferate and lead to severe disease for their host.¹³³

Adherence to host cell surfaces is often the first step in the establishment of bacterial disease. For extracellular pathogens, adherence allows bacteria to withstand the mechanical clearing mechanisms of the host; for intracellular pathogens, adherence is often a prerequisite for uptake invasion. Adhesins are bacterial components that mediate interaction between the bacterium and the host cell surface. Bacterial engagement of host cell receptors can be a means of targeting a pathogen to a particular niche, co-opting underlying signaling pathways, establishing persistent infections and inducing invasion.¹³⁴

Many bacterial pathogens have evolved the capacity to adhere to CAMs (cell adhesion molecules). CAMs are cell-surface receptors that mediate cell-cell and cell-extracellular-matrix (ECM) interactions. Generally, they can be classified into four main groups: integrins, cadherins, members of the immunoglobulin superfamily of CAMs (IgCAMs), and selectins.¹³⁵

6. Sample collection

The interpretation and the accuracy of the microbiological results still depend to a great extent on the quality of the samples and their processing within the Microbiology laboratory. The type of specimen, the appropriate time to obtain the sample, the way of sampling, the storage and transport are critical points in the diagnostic process. The availability of new laboratory techniques for unusual pathogens, makes necessary the review and update of all the steps involved in the processing of the samples.¹³⁶

6.1 Collection of sterile body fluids

Sterile body fluids represent important specimens for the diagnosis of infectious diseases and should be utilized to the fullest extent to identify the etiologic agent of infection. Rapid information is available from microscopic examination and complete identification is determined from subsequent cultures. Noncultural methods are also available or being developed to aid in the early recognition of the cause of infection.¹³⁷

6.1.1. Collection of Cerebrospinal Fluid

Lumbar puncture (LP), also referred to as “spinal tap,” is a commonly performed procedure that involves obtaining and sampling cerebrospinal fluid from the spinal cord. It was developed by Heinrich Quincke in the late 19th Century. It is the gold standard diagnostic procedure in the diagnosis of meningitis, subarachnoid hemorrhage, and certain neurological disorders. It is also used in the measurement of intracranial pressure and administration of medications or diagnostic agents.¹³⁸

As with any procedure, preparation is key to ensure safety and improve the likelihood of success. First, begin by assessing whether there are any contraindications to performing the procedure. Clinical signs of or risk factors for increased intracranial pressure, coagulopathy, or thrombocytopenia should be evaluated before performing a lumbar puncture. Review the indications listed for head CT before performing a lumbar puncture (LP).

Before beginning, the procedure, as well as risks and benefits, should be explained to the patient. Informed consent should be obtained before performing the procedure.¹³⁸ The positioning of the patient in either a lateral recumbent position or sitting position may be used. The lateral recumbent position is preferred as it will allow an accurate

measurement of opening pressure, and it also reduces the risk of post-lumbar puncture headache. The patient should be instructed to assume the fetal position, which involves the flexion of the spine. It may be helpful to instruct the patient to flex their back "like a cat." By doing so, the space between the spinous processes increases, allowing for easier needle insertion. To help keep the needle at the midline during insertion, the lumbar spine should be perpendicular to the table in the sitting position and parallel to the table if in the recumbent position.

The ideal insertion point of the spinal needle should be either in the interspinous area between L4 and L5 or L3 and L4. Using these landmarks will avoid inadvertent damage to the conus medullaris, which typically terminates at L1. Palpation of landmarks along the back of the patient is used to locate the ideal insertion point for the needle. Certain conditions such as obesity, scoliosis, and degenerative disc disease may make palpation of landmarks more difficult. A line should be drawn between the superior aspects of the iliac crests. This line is referred to as the intercrystal line or Tuffier line. This line typically intersects the spine along the L4 spinous process; however, this should only serve as a general reference as there are anatomical variations from person to person. The intercrystal line may intersect at a higher level than L4 if the patient is female or obese.¹³⁸

Palpate the landmarks before cleaning the skin and before administration of local anesthesia. Once the interspinous space is palpated, use a skin marking pen to mark the area of needle insertion. The lumbar puncture is considered an aseptic procedure. Don sterile gloves and gown and clean the area with a disinfecting agent. The cleaning agent should be applied to the skin in a widening concentric circular fashion starting at the point of needle insertion and circling outward. Allow the cleaned area to dry. Drape the area with sterile drapes. Prepare CSF collection vials in order by labeling them according to the priority of collection. Typically, they are labeled 1 through 4. After the area has been cleansed and draped, apply a local anesthetic to the area of needle insertion. It is important to have marked the area of needle insertion before administration of local anesthetic as it may result in loss of landmarks.¹³⁷

6.1.2. Collection of Pericardial Fluid

Pericardiocentesis is a procedure that involves accessing the pericardial space around the heart with a needle or cannula to aspirate fluid for drainage, analysis, or both.¹³⁹ Pericardiocentesis is a procedure performed to remove pericardial fluid from the pericardial sac. It is often performed in the setting of pericardial tamponade to correct hypotension due to decreased stroke volume from extrinsic compression of the chambers of the heart.¹⁴⁰

Pericardiocentesis is performed for medical patients either as a therapeutic or diagnostic procedure. Pericardiocentesis is indicated when either an acute or a chronic pericardial effusion causes cardiac tamponade. Pericardiocentesis in acute or chronic pericardial effusions without evidence of cardiac tamponade and other non-emergent situations is indicated for the diagnosis of the underlying etiology of the effusion by obtaining pericardial fluid for laboratory analysis, for palliation of symptoms including dyspnea or edema, or to prevent progression of the effusion to pericardial tamponade an emergent situation. In the acute setting, only a small amount of pericardiac fluid (100-150 mL) is necessary to cause cardiac tamponade, while in chronic pericardial effusions, as much as 1-2 L of pericardial fluid may accumulate as long as the parietal pericardium has adequate time to adjust to the increasing volume. Pericardiocentesis can be performed at the bedside in the same manner as for traumatic pericardial tamponade, or the patient may be resuscitated with IV fluids and taken to the cardiac catheterization lab for pericardiocentesis performed using TTE or fluoroscopic guidance and with monitoring of right-sided heart pressures. In situations where re-accumulation of pericardial fluid is expected, a pericardial drain may be to facilitate serial drainage.^{140,}

6.1.3. Collection of Plural Fluid

Thoracocentesis (from the Greek words, thorax + centesis, puncture) is an invasive procedure associated with removal of fluid or air from the pleural space for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes.^{141,142} This can be performed by inserting carefully a needle into the pleural space in order to aspirate the pathologically collected fluid or air and allow the compressed lung to re-inflate. Ultrasound guided needle aspiration is a very useful technique and, whenever is possible, should be performed in order to reduce complications. The procedure is performed by an experienced interventional radiologist

or a well-trained physician with the patient in a seated position (unless the clinical situation does not allow).¹⁴¹ Ultrasound-guided thoracentesis is a valuable technique that could be performed in order to reduce complications especially in patients who are on mechanical ventilator support (iatrogenic pneumothorax in a patient on positive-pressure mechanical ventilatory support is particularly dangerous because there is a high risk of tension pneumothorax) or in case of a small effusion. The recommended location for the needle insertion varies depending upon the source. Some sources recommend the mid-axillary line in the 6th, 7th, or 8th intercostal space. It is critical that the patient hold his or her breath to avoid piercing of the lung.^{141,143}

The pleural fluid collection is located and marked under real-time ultrasound guidance. Multiple scans are obtained in transverse, oblique, and sagittal planes. After preparation of the site, needle insertion is performed at the marked point in the middle of the appropriate intercostal space, with the insertion assembly held at the same angle as was the probe, taking into account to avoid the blood vessels and nerves that run down the caudal edge of each rib. The procedure must be performed under aseptic conditions using: (I) local anesthetic, sterile needle; (II) butterfly; (III) a plastic flexible catheter-needle system; (IV) three-way; (V) syringe. Lung sliding should be assessed before and following thoracentesis. The loss of lung sliding following thoracentesis when it was present before the procedure indicates that there has been a procedure-related pneumothorax. The finding of lung sliding following thoracentesis obviates the need for chest radiography performed in order to rule out pneumothorax.^{141,143} There is a suggestion that drainage of large amounts of fluid at ultrasound-guided thoracentesis is a risk factor for pneumothorax.¹⁴¹

6.1.4. Collection of Peritoneal Fluid

Paracentesis is a procedure performed to obtain a small sample of or drain ascitic fluid for both diagnostic or therapeutic purposes.¹⁴⁴ A needle or catheter is inserted into the peritoneal cavity and ascitic fluid is removed for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes. The fluid may be used to determine the etiology of ascites and evaluate for cancer or infection.¹⁴⁴

The preferred site for the procedure is in either lower quadrant of the abdomen lateral to the rectus sheath. Placing the patient in the lateral decubitus position can aid in

identifying fluid pockets in patients with lower fluid volumes. Ask the patient to empty his or her bladder before starting the procedure.

Bedside ultrasound should be used to identify an appropriate location for the procedure. Ultrasound can confirm the presence of fluid and identify an area with a sufficient amount of fluid for aspiration, thereby decreasing the incidence of both unsuccessful aspiration and complications. Ultrasound increases the success rate of paracentesis and helps to prevent an unnecessary invasive procedure in some patients. The procedure can be performed either after marking the site of insertion or in real time by advancing the needle under direct ultrasound guidance.¹⁴⁴

6.1.5. Collection of Synovial Fluid

Arthrocentesis is a procedure performed to collect synovial fluid from joint spaces for the identification of a disease process or the relief of painful or bothersome symptoms. There are numerous indications for joint fluid aspiration, the most important of which includes the evaluation of synovial fluid for evidence of infection or inflammation. While the procedure specifics vary depending on the joint being aspirated, the general technique and steps remain consistent. The procedure tends to be very safe overall with few complications if performed correctly, and only a small number of contraindications.¹⁴⁵

Define the joint anatomy by palpating the surrounding bony landmarks. Ultrasound may be helpful in locating effusions. Select a puncture site and an approach to the joint based on the appropriate anatomy, avoiding tendons, major blood vessels, and major nerves. Apply the antiseptic solution to the area of needle insertion and surrounding skin. Allow the skin to dry and then put down the sterile drape surrounding the area of needle insertion. Using a 25 gauge to 27 gauge needle, first create a wheal of local anesthetic at the point of insertion. After the skin is anesthetized, infiltrate the skin down to the area of the joint capsule. For extremely painful joints, a regional nerve block can be used. Attach a larger needle of appropriate length to an appropriately sized syringe. Insert the needle into the joint space along the anesthetized track. For draining larger effusions, a three-way stopcock can be placed between the needle and the syringe. To change the syringe during the procedure, grasp the hub of the needle with a sterile hemostat and hold it tightly while removing the syringe. An attempt should be made to remove as much fluid or blood as possible. If fluid stops flowing, the joint is

either drained completely, the needle tip is dislodged, or debris is obstructing the needle. Slightly advance or retract the tip, rotate the bevel, or aspirate less forcefully. Place fluid into appropriate tubes and send the synovial fluid for studies as indicated by the clinical scenario. Place a dressing or bandage over the puncture site, and apply pressure to achieve hemostasis.¹⁴⁵

6.1.6. Collection of Bile

Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) is a combined endoscopic and fluoroscopic procedure in which an upper endoscope is led into a second part of the duodenum, making it possible for passage of other tools via the major duodenal papilla into the biliary and pancreatic ducts. Contrast material may be injected in these ducts, allowing for radiologic visualization and therapeutic interventions when indicated. ERCP initially started as a diagnostic procedure through cannulation of the pancreatic and biliary ducts but has evolved over the years to a predominantly therapeutic tool. Difficult biliary cannulation is proposed to be defined as cannulation attempts duration of more than 5 minutes, more than five cannulation attempts, or at least two pancreatic guidewire passages. Direct visualization of the ducts is done through cholangiopancreatoscopy.¹⁴⁶

The American Society for Gastrointestinal Endoscopy (ASGE) issued a guideline for routine laboratory testing before endoscopic procedures. They recommend against routine radiographic, cardiac, or laboratory testing before endoscopy for otherwise healthy patients, but recommend selective testing based on patient's and procedure's risk factors. They recommend a pregnancy test when appropriate, hemoglobin/hematocrit, and blood typing and screening in patients with anemia, bleeding, or when blood loss is expected during the procedure. Coagulation studies are also indicated in patients with bleeding or bleeding disorders, biliary diseases, or poor nutrition. A chest radiograph is only indicated if the patient has respiratory or cardiac symptoms. Other laboratory testing should be ordered based on the patient's medical history. As with other procedures that require sedation, patients need to be fasting before the procedure.

Antibiotic prophylaxis is not routinely recommended prior to ERCP. However, it is recommended in patients with a liver transplant or biliary obstruction. Biliary flora,

including enterococci and gram-negative organisms, should be covered, and antibiotics should be continued after ERCP if biliary drainage is incomplete.¹⁴⁶

7. Laboratory Diagnosis

Accurate and timely diagnostic microbiology is as essential for nosocomial infection control as it is for the clinical management of patients' infections. Although many infections can be diagnosed on the basis of clinical criteria alone, cultures and other laboratory tests allow infections to be diagnosed with much greater certainty, and certain infections.¹⁴⁷

7.1. Conventional Methods

Conventional identification of bacteria consists of performing Gram stain followed by bacterial identification and antibiotic-susceptibility testing. The process from start to finish can take up to five days, which can delay time to antibiotic de-escalation.¹⁴⁸ Antibiotic susceptibility standards in the U.S. are determined by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), which mostly refers to standards set by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). Standards may vary in other countries, which can lead to discrepancies in the definition of antibiotic susceptibility; this has led to the creation of the National Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing Committee for the USA (USCAST). This committee works with the European Union Committee for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing to normalize standards on an international level. The determination of antibiotic susceptibility uses quantitative data that is further split into qualitative categories.¹⁴⁸

Quantitative testing is typically performed by identification of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). The MIC is the lowest concentration of antibiotic needed to inhibit the growth of an organism. The lowest MIC does not always correlate to the most effective treatment, as different antibiotics achieve different concentrations in different sites.¹⁴⁹

To determine qualitative categories, specific MIC values, also known as breakpoints, are used to classify bacteria as susceptible, intermediate, or resistant to a specific antibiotic. To determine breakpoints, the CLSI uses pharmacokinetic, pharmacodynamic, resistance mechanisms, and clinical data. The CLSI defines as

susceptible those isolates that are inhibited by typical achievable concentrations of an antibiotic when the dosage recommended to treat the infection site is used.¹⁴⁸

The susceptible dose-dependent category is determined when a dosing regimen is required that results in more drug exposure than that which is used in the susceptible category to achieve clinical efficacy. The intermediate category includes isolates that approach usually attainable levels in blood and tissue by an antibiotic, and response rates are lower than susceptible isolates. Lastly, the resistant category encompasses isolates that are not inhibited by the usual achievable concentrations of an antibiotic agent or for which resistance mechanisms are likely and clinical efficacy of antibiotics has not been reliably shown.

The disk diffusion, or Kirby-Bauer, method, is a common test used to determine antibiotic susceptibility. Diffusion testing works by placing an antibiotic disc onto an agar plate containing bacteria. The plate is incubated for up to 24 hours and during this time, the antibiotic diffuses throughout the plate, forming a concentration gradient surrounding the disc.¹⁴⁸ For example, the highest antibiotic concentration in a set of wells could be 4.0 ug/mL. The next well after one dilution would have a concentration of 2.0 ug/mL, then 1.0 ug/mL after two dilutions, and 0.5 ug/mL after three dilutions. Dilution test results can vary, and one-fold dilution error is common. For example, if the MIC is determined to be 1 ug/mL, the true MIC range could be from 0.5 to 2 ug/mL. This can be problematic if the range includes a susceptible and an intermediate MIC value. Broth dilution consists of microdilution and macrodilution. Although they are similar, the methods differ primarily by the modality that is used to perform susceptibility testing (wells or tubes).¹⁴⁸

Broth microdilution is performed by placing different antibiotics with varying concentrations in wells that contain liquid media. Bacteria are added to each well, and the tray is incubated. The presence of bacterial growth is then identified through visual inspection of the plate. The MIC of the broth microdilution test is determined when no growth is observed with a particular antibiotic. An advantage of this test is that more than one antibiotic can be tested at a time. Disadvantages are that broth dilution is labor-intensive and time-consuming, and potential procedural errors may occur.

The agar dilution test is similar to the broth dilution test, the major difference being that it uses physical media as opposed to liquid media. Agar dilution is performed by placing

standard concentrations of the organism on agar plates that vary in concentration of antibiotic.¹⁴⁸ The MIC is determined in the first test tube that demonstrates no growth of the organism. This test is commonly used when testing multiple bacteria against a particular antibiotic. Agar dilution is also labor-intensive and time-consuming, and it cannot test more than one antibiotic at a time.¹⁴⁸

7.2 Automated System

Automated systems have the advantage of being less labor-intensive and of enabling quicker reporting of results. These systems primarily use dilution principles to determine antibiotic susceptibility. Fully automatic systems will introduce bacteria to a panel, incubate them, then read and interpret the susceptibility results. Automated tests determine MIC through the use of algorithms and allow rules that predict resistance to other antibiotics. Also, these systems can save results to be used in the creation of antibiograms along with other reports. The FDA sets standards for the approval of automated systems, which include a rate of false resistance of less than 3% and a false susceptibility of less than 1.5% on the lower end of the 95% confidence interval (CI) and less than 7.5% on the upper end of the 95% CI.¹⁴⁹

8. Phenotypic Test for detecting different phenotypes (drug resistant) among body fluid infections.

The development of antibiotic resistances in common pathogens is an increasing challenge for therapy of infections and especially severe complications like sepsis. To prevent administration of broad-spectrum and potentially non-effective antibiotics, the susceptibility spectrum of the pathogens underlying the infection has to be determined. Current phenotypic standard methods for antibiotic susceptibility testing (AST) require the isolation of pathogens from the patient and the subsequent culturing in the presence of antibiotics leading to results only after 24-72 h.¹⁴⁸

8.1. Metallo Beta Lactamase (MBL)

Screening and confirmation of Metallo Beta Lactamase (MBL): Screening and confirmation for the detection of MBL is done by EDTA-impregnated imipenem disc. For confirmatory test imipenem (10µg) disc is placed apart from imipenem-EDTA. Plates are incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hrs. After incubation, if the zone of inhibition with

imipenem EDTA was ≥ 5 mm than imipenem discs alone, then the test is considered a positive result.¹⁵⁰

MBLs constitute molecularly diverse group of broad-spectrum beta-lactamases. A metallo β -lactamase enzyme was first reported in *Bacillus cereus* in mid-1960s.¹³⁷ MBLs belong to class B of Ambler classification system. It can be further subdivided into three subclasses 'B1', 'B2' and 'B3'.¹³⁸ These enzymes require divalent cations of zinc (Zn^{2+}) as co-factors for enzymatic activity and are universally inhibited by ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) and other chelating agents of divalent cations.¹⁵¹

8.2. Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL)

Screening of ESBL is done as per the CLSI guidelines, if isolated Gram negative bacilli is resistant to ceftazidime (30 μ g) then it is suspected to be an ESBL producer. Phenotypic confirmation of ESBL detection test is done by combined disc diffusion test. After incubation, if the increase in inhibition zone with ceftazidime + clavulanic acid disc is ≥ 5 mm than the ceftazidime alone, it is interpreted as ESBL producer.¹⁵⁰

Extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) are rapidly evolving group of β -lactamase enzymes that contribute to resistance against beta-lactam antibiotics. These enzymes have the ability to hydrolyze and cause resistance to extended spectrum cephalosporins such as oxyiminocephalosporins (cefotaxime, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, cefuroxime and cefepime) and monobactams (aztreonam), but not the cephamycins (cefoxitin and cefotetan) or carbapenems (imipenem, meropenem and ertapenem). ESBLs belong to class A of Ambler classification system that includes enzymes acted by serine based mechanism and inhibits by clavulanic acid.¹⁵² This enzyme was first detected in 1979 in the family Enterobacteriaceae. ESBL producing organisms are often resistant to several other classes of antibiotics because the genetic elements carrying gene encoding ESBLs often carry other resistance determinants.¹⁵³

8.3. Ampicillin Class C Beta Lactamase (AmpC)

This screening test is performed by cefoxitin (30 μ g) disc test. If the isolated organisms show less than 18 mm inhibition zone, it is further subjected to confirmatory test. After preparing the lawn a cefoxitin disc and a cefoxitin + cloxacillin disc were placed 20mm apart and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hrs. After incubation, if the zone of inhibition

with cefoxitin+ cloxacillin is ≥ 4 mm than the cefoxitin, then it is considered as AmpC producer.¹⁵⁰

AmpC enzymes constitute another large group of broad-spectrum β -lactamases and belong to class C of the Ambler classification scheme and 1 β -lactamases group of the Bush- Jacoby-Medeiros classification scheme. These enzymes can hydrolyze penicillins, cephalosporins (including the third-generation but usually not the fourth-generation cephalosporins), monobactams as well as cephamycins (cefoxitin, cephalothin, cefotetan, cefmetazole). AmpC type enzymes are generally poorly inhibited by β -lactamase inhibitors, especially clavulanic acid.¹⁵⁴ The features that discriminate AmpC β -lactamases (AmpC-BLs) from ESBLs include: hydrolysis of cephamycins and resistance to β -lactamase inhibitors. Those AmpC genes which are present on the bacterial chromosome are usually inducible in nature. These genes are generally repressed and produce low levels of AmpC-BLs. They become de-repressed (induced) by a number of β -lactam antibiotics e.g., benzyl penicillin and narrow spectrum cephalosporins such as cefoxitin and hyperproduce AmpC-BLs. Thus, strains carrying inducible AmpC genes are intrinsically resistant to those β -lactam antibiotics which induce them. In contrast, AmpC genes which are located on plasmids are commonly non-inducible. They constitutively produce AmpC enzymes. However, some plasmid mediated AmpC enzymes have been reported to be inducible. AmpC-BLs has minimum activity against carbapenems and monobactam (aztreonam).¹⁵⁵

8.4. Carbapenem Resistant Enterobacterales

Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) are a family of bacteria which are very difficult to treat because they are highly resistant to antibiotics. In general, common bacteria such as *Klebsiella species* and *E. coli* can become carbapenem resistant. This is due to bacterial synthesis of a carbapenemase enzyme that deactivates carbapenems by breaking down the beta-lactam part of the molecules.¹⁵⁶

8.5. Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)

Prevalent MRSA infection outside the healthcare setting was first reported in 1982 in Detroit, Michigan, among intravenous (IV) drug users.¹⁵⁷ Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was identified in clinical isolates only a few years after the introduction of this drug in clinical practice. This resistance trait has become

common and spread worldwide due to the diffusion of epidemic clones, and MRSA has become one of the most frequently isolated nosocomial pathogens.¹⁵⁸

8.6 Vancomycin Resistant Enterococcus (VRE)

Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococci* (VRE) cause substantial morbidity and mortality in immune-suppressed patients.¹⁵⁹ The first reports of VRE, encoded by the *vanA* gene,^{57a,57b} appeared in 1988. US CDC surveillance efforts indicate that, from January 1989 to early 1993, there was a 20-fold increase in the percentage of VRE in hospital-acquired infections in ICUs, and that many of these VRE were resistant to all available antibiotics. As of December 2003, the incidence of VRE was 28.5%, up 12% over the mean rate of resistance found in the prior 5 years.¹⁶⁰

MATERIAL & METHODS

The present study, "STUDY OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES AND ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN IN BODY FLUIDS OF PATIENTS FROM A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL," was conducted in the Department of Microbiology at Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences, Krishna Hospital and Medical Research Centre, Karad, Dist. Satara.

Study Settings: The study was undertaken in the Department of Microbiology, Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences, Deemed to Be University, Karad.

Study Design: Observational cross-sectional study

Study Period: A study was carried out from November 2021 to November 2023

SAMPLE SIZE:

$$n = 4pq/l^2$$

P= Prevalence of bacterial growth

$$q = 100 - p$$

l = Precision

With the above formula, the sample size for the prevalence of bacterial infection of body fluids with the following references is as per the given table No.1.

Table No. 1 Sample size

Table for sample size				
Author	Place	Year	Prevalence of bacterial growth (%)	Sample Size
Madigubba H. ¹⁶¹	Mysore, Karnataka	2020	29.9%	171
Harshika Y K ²	Hubli, Karnataka	2018	22%	140
Sharma R⁵	New Delhi	2017	30%	171

$$n = 4pq/l^2$$

$$= 4 \times 30 \times 70/7^2$$

$$= 171$$

So, in the present study, a minimum of **171** fluid specimens were required to be studied. To strengthen the study a total of 180 specimens were included.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1) All the specimens of sterile body fluids received from hospitalized patient in

Krishna hospital Karad

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1) Blood and urine specimens

2) Delay of fluid transport of more than two hours after collection

ETHICAL CLEARANCE:

The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences, Deemed to Be University, Karad. via protocol number 069/2021-2022.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data were entered into MS Excel and analyzed. Results were expressed as percentages and p-values, determined by Chi-square test using GraphPad Instant software. An association or difference is considered significant if the probability is less than 0.05.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data from the patients included in the study were recorded using a structured Proforma. This included details such as name, age, sex, address, IPD number, etc., along with other information like date of admission and clinical diagnosis.

SPECIMEN COLLECTION:

After receiving approval from the Institute's Ethics Committee, specimens of sterile body fluids such as cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), pleural fluid, pericardial fluid, bile, peritoneal/ascitic fluid, and synovial fluid were collected after obtaining patient consent. All specimens were collected in sterile containers and transported to the microbiology laboratory within 2 hours.

SAMPLE PROCESSING:

All the specimens were processed in the laboratory using standard microbiological procedures. Samples were subjected to Gram stain and then inoculated on enriched media such as blood agar and chocolate agar, along with differential media such as MacConkey agar (Himedia, Mumbai, India) for culture using the four-quadrant streak method. The inoculated plates were checked for bacterial growth the following day. All bacterial growth was examined for colony characteristics, including Gram staining, motility, and biochemical tests for species identification. Samples were considered sterile after 48 hours of incubation only. (Bacterial isolates were identified following the standard protocol described in Practical Microbiology of Mackie McCartney, 14th edition.)¹⁶²

Direct microscopy: Gram Stain:

The heat-fixed smear of each specimen was processed using the Gram stain technique and examined under the oil immersion objective of the light microscope. The smears were checked for the presence of Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms.

Identification of Isolates:

Bacterial isolates were identified based on their characteristics such as colony morphology, Gram stain, motility, catalase test, coagulase test, oxidase test, and biochemical reactions.

Table No. 2 Biochemical Reactions

Organisms	Gram stain	Catalase	Oxidase	Indole	MR	Citrate	Urease	TSI
<i>E. coli</i>	Gram negative bacilli	+	-	+	+	-	-	A/A Gas
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Gram negative bacilli	+	-	-	-	+	+	K/K
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Gram negative bacilli	+	-	-	-	+	+	A/A Gas
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii complex</i>	Gram negative coccobacilli	+	-	-	-	+	-	K/K
<i>Enterobacter cloacae complex</i>	Gram negative bacilli	+	-	-	-	+	-	A/A Gas

A/A Gas = Acid/Acid Gas

K/K = Alkaline/Alkaline

A/A Gas, H₂S = Acid/Acid Gas, H₂S

TEST PROCEDURE:

Catalase Test:

A small amount of the culture to be tested was picked from an agar plate using a clean, sterile thin glass rod.

The culture was then inserted into 1 ml of 3% Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution in a small, clean tube.

The production of gas bubbles from the surface of the test tube indicated a catalase positive reaction. The Catalase Test is considered positive for Gram-negative organisms.

Oxidase Test:

The test was conducted using the dry filter paper method. Whatman's No.1 filter paper was soaked in a freshly prepared 1% solution of tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride.

The colony to be tested was picked up with a clean, sterile thin glass rod and smeared over the moist area.

A positive reaction was indicated by the appearance of an intense deep-purple color within 5-10 seconds.

Indole Test:

This test was performed in a peptone water culture by inoculating the colony to be tested and incubating it for 48 hours at 37°C.

After incubation, 0.5 ml of Kovac's reagent was added and shaken gently. Kovac's reagent was prepared by dissolving 10 gm of paradimethylaminobenzaldehyde in 150 ml of amyl alcohol or isoamyl alcohol, followed by the slow addition of 50 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCL).

This test demonstrates the production of indole from tryptophan. A red color indicates a positive reaction.

Methyl-Red Test:

This test was employed to detect the production of acid during the fermentation of glucose and the maintenance of a pH below 4.5 in an old culture.

A colony from a young culture was inoculated into Glucose Phosphate Peptone Water and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours.

After incubation, five drops of 0.04% solution of methyl red reagent were added and mixed.

Formation of a bright red color signified a positive reaction, while the development of a yellow color indicated a negative reaction.

Citrate Utilization Test:

This test checks the ability of an organism to utilize citrate as the sole carbon and energy source for growth and an ammonium salt as the sole source of nitrogen.

Simmons citrate medium (modified) were used with agar and an indicator.

The medium was inoculated from a saline suspension of the organism to be tested and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

A blue color with a streak of growth indicated a positive reaction, while a green color and no growth indicated a negative reaction.

Urease Test:

This test was conducted using Christensen's urease medium by inoculating the colony to be examined over the entire slope surface and incubating at 37°C for 24 hours.

Urease positive cultures produced a purple-pink color.

Urease-producing bacteria reduce urea to ammonia, which is responsible for the color change.

Triple Sugar Iron Agar (TSI) Test:

The Triple Sugar Iron agar medium contains three sugars: glucose, lactose, and sucrose in a ratio of 1:10:10. Ferrous sulfate and phenol red serve as indicators of H₂S production and acidification, respectively.

The colony to be examined was inoculated into TSI by first stabbing with a sterile straight wire loop through the center of the medium to the bottom of the tube and then streaking the surface of the agar slant, followed by incubation at 37°C for 18-24 hours.

The results were observed as follows:

1. Alkaline slant with no color change in the butt indicated glucose and lactose were not utilized.
2. Alkaline slant with acidic butt indicated glucose fermentation.
3. Acidic slant with acidic butt indicated lactose, glucose, or sucrose fermentation.
4. Formation of a black precipitate in the butt indicated ferrous sulfide and H₂S gas production.
5. Cracks or bubbles in the tube indicated the production of CO₂ and H₂.

ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY TEST:

The antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed for all isolates using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion technique under Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI 2022) guidelines.¹⁶³ Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was done using the following antibiotic discs.

Antimicrobials for Gram-Positive Bacteria:

The antibiotics tested for Gram positive bacteria are given below:

Ampicillin (10µg), Gentamicin (10µg), Ciprofloxacin (5µg), Tetracycline (30µg), Clindamycin (10µg), Vancomycin (30µg), Cefoxitin (30µg), Co-trimoxazole (1.25/23.75µg), Amikacin (10µg), Erythromycin (10µg), Cefepime (30µg), Levofloxacin (5µg), Linezolid (30µg).

Antimicrobials for Gram-Negative Bacteria:

The antibiotics tested for Gram negative bacteria are given below:

Amikacin (30µg), Gentamicin (10µg), Ciprofloxacin (5µg), Cefotaxime(30µg), Imipenem (10µg), Cefoxitin (30µg), Ceftazidime (30µg), Piperacillin-tazobactam (100/10µg) Cefoperazone-sulbactam (75/30µg), Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (1.225/23.75µg), Fosfomycin (200µg),

Inoculum Preparation:

Four to five colonies with the same morphology were selected from an agar culture plate using a sterile bacteriological loop. The growth was inoculated into a broth medium and incubated for 3-5 hours to achieve a turbid suspension, which was then compared with the 0.5 McFarland standard.¹⁶³

0.5 McFarland Turbidity Standard Preparation:

This standard was prepared by adding 0.5 ml of 1% anhydrous BaCl₂ to 9.95 ml of 1% H₂SO₄ in a test tube, which was then sealed and stored in the refrigerator.¹⁶³

Inoculation and Incubation:

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed by the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, adhering to the CLSI 2022 guidelines. A bacterial inoculum was spread uniformly over Muller Hinton agar plates using a submerged swab. Antibiotic discs from Himedia were placed on the agar surface with sterile forceps within 15 minutes, and each disc was pressed gently to ensure proper contact with the medium. The plates were then inverted to avoid moisture build-up that might impact the test outcome. After incubation at 37°C for 24 hours, the inhibition zones around each disc were measured with a standardized zone measurement scale, and results were interpreted according to CLSI standards.¹⁶³

PHENOTYPIC TEST FOR GRAM NEGATIVE ORGANISMS:

1) DETECTION OF EXTENDED SPECTRUM BETA LACTAMASE (ESBL) PRODUCTION:

Screening Test: Isolated Gram-negative bacilli were suspected to be ESBL producers if they were resistant to the following drugs: aztreonam (30µg), cefotaxime (30µg), cefpodoxime (10µg), ceftazidime (30µg), and ceftriaxone (30µg). ESBL production in Gram-negative bacilli was confirmed by phenotypic methods.

Combined disc diffusion Test: This test is specifically designed to detect ESBL production in Enterobacteriaceae. A Ceftazidime disc and a ceftazidime + Clavulanic acid (30 µg + 10 µg) disc were placed 20 mm apart, center to center, and incubated aerobically at 37°C for 16-18 hours. A positive test result is defined as a 5 mm or greater increase in the size of the zone diameter for ceftazidime tested in combination with clavulanic acid versus the zone for either antibiotic tested alone.

Figure No. 1 ESBL producing Gram-negative bacteria

2) DETECTION OF METALLO BETA LACTAMASE (MBL):

This test detects Gram-negative bacteria that produce Metallo-beta lactamase.

The screening test for MBL production is performed using an Imipenem disc (10 µg).

The screened isolates (Imipenem resistant) are further confirmed by the combined disc method using Imipenem (10 µg) alone and in combination with EDTA.

After overnight incubation at 37°C, if the increase in the inhibition zone with the Imipenem-EDTA disc is greater than or equal to 7 mm compared to the Imipenem (10 µg) disc alone, it is interpreted as an MBL producer.

Figure No. 2 MBL producing Gram-negative bacteria

3) DETECTION OF AmpC BETA-LACTAMASE PRODUCTION:

An inoculum of the test organism was prepared and matched with a turbidity of 0.5 McFarland standard. Test and control organisms were inoculated on Mueller-Hinton agar to give a semi-confluent growth. A Cefoxitin disc and a Cefoxitin + Cloxacillin disc were placed 20 mm apart and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours. After incubation, if the inhibition zone with the Cefoxitin + Cloxacillin disc is greater than or equal to 4 mm compared to the Cefoxitin disc alone, the organism is identified as an AmpC producer.¹⁶⁴

Figure No. 3 AmpC producing Gram-negative bacteria

GRAM STAIN

Figure No. 4 Gram positive cocci in cluster (Coagulase positive *Staphylococcus*)

Figure No. 5 Gram negative bacteria (*E. coli*)

GROWTH ON AGAR PLATES

Figure No. 6 *E. coli* on MacConkey's agar

Figure No. 7 *K. pneumoniae* on MacConkey's agar

Figure No. 8 *A. baumannii* on MacConkey's agar

Figure No. 9 *P. aeruginosa* on MacConkey's agar

Figure No. 10 *E. cloacae* on MacConkey's agar

Figure No. 11 *K. pneumoniae* on blood agar

Figure No. 12 *E. coli* on blood agar

Figure No. 13 *A. baumannii* complex on blood agar

Figure No. 14 *P. aeruginosa* on blood agar

Figure No. 15 *Enterobacter cloacae* complex
on blood agar

Figure No. 16 *S. aureus* on blood agar

Figure No. 17 *S. aureus* on nutrient agar

Figure N0. 18 *S. pneumoniae* on chocolate agar

Figure No. 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* on Muller-Hinton agar by Kirby Baur disk diffusion method

Figure N0. 20 Rapid tests

Oxidase test- Positive

Oxidase test- Negative

Slide coagulase Test

Tube coagulase Test

Slide catalase Test

Figure No. 21 Biochemical test

Biochemical reaction of *E. coli*

Biochemical test from left to right- TSI, indole, MR, citrate, urease

Biochemical reaction of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Biochemical test from left to right- TSI, indole, MR, citrate, urease

Biochemical reaction of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Biochemical test from left to right- TSI, indole, MR, citrate, urease

Biochemical reaction of *Acinetobacter baumannii* complex

Biochemical test from left to right- TSI, indole, MR, citrate, urease

Biochemical reaction of *Enterobacter cloacae* complex

Biochemical test from left to right- Indole, MR, citrate, urease, TSI

RESULTS AND OBSERVATION

Table No. 3 Age, Sex wise distribution of Sterile body fluids

Age	Female (%)	Male (%)	Total (%)
0 – 20	4(2.23)	7(3.89)	11(6.12)
21 -40	9(5)	43(23.88)	52(28.88)
41 -60	15(8.33)	48(26.67)	63(35)
62 – 80	17(9.44)	33(18.33)	50(27.77)
81 – 100	1(0.55)	3(1.68)	4(2.23)
Total	46(25.55)	134(74.45)	180(100)

Fig. No. 22 Age, Sex wise distribution of Sterile body fluids

- Maximum sterile body fluids were from 41 – 60 age group 63 (35%) followed by 21 – 40 age group 52 (28.88%). Least were from 81 – 100 age group 4 (2.23%)
- Maximum males were from 41 – 60 age group 48 (26.67%) followed by 21 – 40 age group 43 (23.88%). Least were from 81 – 100 age group 3 (1.68%).
- Maximum females were from 41 – 60 age group 15 (8.33%) followed by 21 – 40 age group 9 (5%). Least were from 81 – 100 age group 1 (0.55%).

Table No. 4 Gender wise distribution of various body fluids

Sr. No	Body fluids	Total number	Female (%)	Male (%)
1	CSF	48	14(29.16)	34(70.84)
2	Pleural fluid	53	9(16.98)	44(83.02)
3	Peritoneal fluid	23	7(30.43)	16(69.57)
4	Ascitic fluid	50	12(24)	38(76)
5	Pericardial fluid	4	2(50)	2(50)
6	Bile	1	1(100)	0(0)
7	Synovial fluid	1	1(100)	0(0)
Total		180	46(25.55)	134(74.45)

Fig. No. 23 Gender wise distribution of various body fluids

Table No. 5 Distribution of body fluids in hospital

Sr. No	Department	Number	Percentage (%)
1	Medicine ICU	83	(46.12)
2	Medicine ward	29	(16.12)
3	Oncology	7	(3.88)
4	Surgery ICU	24	(13.33)
5	Surgery ward	18	(10)
6	Emergency department	14	(7.77)
7	NICU	3	(1.67)
8	OBGY	2	(1.11)
Total		180	(100)

Fig. No. 24 Distribution of body fluids in hospitals

Maximum sterile body fluids were from Medicine ICU 83(46.12%) followed by Medicine ward 29(16.12%), surgery ICU 24(13.33%), Emergency department

14(7.77%), surgery ward 18(10%), oncology 7(3.88%), NICU 3(1.67) OBGY 2(1.11%).

Table No. 6 Distribution of Growth among different Body fluids

Sr. No.	Body Fluids	Total No. (%)	Growth (%)	No Growth (%)
1	CSF	48(26.67)	4(8.33)	44(91.67)
2	Pleural Fluid	53(29.45)	11(20.75)	42(79.25)
3	Peritoneal Fluid	23(12.78)	7(30.43)	16(69.57)
4	Ascitic Fluid	50(27.78)	9(18)	41(82)
5	Pericardial Fluid	4(2.22)	1(25)	3(75)
6	Bile	1(0.55)	0(0)	1(100)
7	Synovial Fluid	1(0.55)	0(0)	1(100)
Total		180	32(17.77)	148(82.23)

Fig. No. 25 Distribution of Growth among different Body fluids

A total 180 different body fluids were collected from suspected patients which included CSF samples, 48 constituted (26.67%), pleural fluid 53(29.45%), peritoneal fluid 23(12.78%), ascitic fluid 50 (27.78%), pericardial fluid 4(2.22%), bile 1(0.55%), synovial fluid 1(0.55%). Out of 180 samples, growth was seen in 32 fluids. Maximum growth seen in peritoneal fluid (30.43%) and no growth seen in bile followed by synovial fluid.

Growth No. 7 Distribution of Gram positive and Gram-negative bacteria among body fluids

Sr. No	Organisms	Number	Percentage
1	Gram positive	5	16%
2	Gram negative	27	84%
Total		32	100%

Fig. No. 26 Distribution of Gram positive and Gram-negative Bacteria amongst Body fluids

Out of 180 samples, 32 fluids were culture positive, with isolation rate of 17.77%. Among the culture positive, the frequency of Gram-negative bacteria was 84% (27/32) and Gram-positive bacteria was 16% (5/32).

Table No. 8 Distribution of Bacterial Isolates in different Body fluids

Sr. No.	Bacterial isolates	CSF (%)	Pleural Fluid (%)	Peritoneal Fluid (%)	Ascitic Fluid (%)	Pericardial Fluid (%)	Total No. (%)
1	<i>E. Coli</i>	-	4 (44.44)	5 (55.56)	-	-	9 (28.12)
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2 (33.3)	1 (16.6)	-	2 (33.3)	1 (16.8)	6 (18.75)
3	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-	-	2 (50)	2 (50)	-	4 (12.5)
4	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii complex</i>	-	2 (66.66)	-	1 (33.34)	-	3 (9.37)
5	<i>Enterobacter cloacae complex</i>	-	-	-	2 (100)	-	2 (6.26)
6	<i>Pseudomonas spec</i>	-	2 (75)	-	1 (25)	-	3 (9.37)
7	<i>Coagulase positive Staphylococcus</i>	1 (33.33)	2 (66.67)	-	-	-	3 (9.37)
8	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	1 (100)	-	-	-	-	1 (3.13)
9	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	-	-	-	1 (100)	-	1 (3.13)
	TOTAL	4 (12.5)	11 (34.38)	7 (21.87)	9 (28.13)	1 (3.12)	32

Fig. No. 27 Distribution of Bacterial Isolates in different Body fluids

Out of 180 cultures positive samples, the predominant organism isolated was *Escherichia coli* 9(28.12%) followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 6(18.75%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 4(12.5%), *Acinetobacter baumannii complex* 3(9.37%), *Enterobacter cloacae complex* 2(6.25%), *Coagulase positive Staphylococcus* 3(9.37%), less commonly isolated were *Streptococcus pneumoniae* 1(3.13%) and *Enterococcus faecium* 1(3.13%).

Table No. 9 Antimicrobial Sensitivity Pattern of Gram-positive Bacteria

Antibiotic	Coagulase positive <i>Staphylococcus</i> (n=3)		<i>Streptococcus</i> <i>pneumoniae</i> (n=1)		<i>Enterococcus</i> <i>faecium</i> (n=1)	
	S (%)	R (%)	S (%)	R (%)	S (%)	R (%)
Gentamicin	1 (33.33)	2 (66.67)	1 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)
Ciprofloxacin	0 (0)	3 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)
Tetracycline	2 (66.67)	1 (33.33)	0 (0)	1 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Clindamycin	1 (33.33)	2 (66.67)	1 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Vancomycin	3 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Cefoxitin	0 (0)	3 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)
Co-trimoxazole	1 (33.33)	2 (66.67)	0 (0)	1 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Amikacin	1 (33.33)	2 (66.67)	1 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)
Erythromycin	0 (0)	3 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Cefepime	0 (0)	3 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)
Levofloxacin	0 (0)	3 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Linezolid	1 (33.33)	2 (66.67)	1 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	0 (0)
Ampicillin	0 (0)	3 (100)	0 (0)	1 (100)	1 (100)	0 (0)

Fig. No. 28 (A) Antimicrobial Sensitivity Pattern of Gram-positive Bacteria

Fig. No. 28 (B) Antimicrobial Resistant Pattern of Gram-positive Isolates

Among Gram positive cocci, *Coagulase positive staphylococcus* was most common isolate, showed 100% sensitive to vancomycin and maximum sensitivity to tetracycline, 2(66.67%) followed by gentamicin, clindamycin, co-trimoxazole, amikacin, linezolid 1(33.33%) and 100% resistance to ciprofloxacin, cefoxitin, erythromycin, cefepime, levofloxacin, ampicillin.

Streptococcus pneumoniae showed 100% sensitivity to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, clindamycin, vancomycin, amikacin, cefepime, levofloxacin, linezolid and 100% resistance to all tetracycline, ceftiofur, co-trimoxazole, erythromycin, ampicillin.

Enterococcus faecium showed 100% sensitivity to tetracycline, clindamycin, vancomycin, co-trimoxazole, erythromycin, levofloxacin, linezolid, ampicillin and 100% resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, ceftiofur, amikacin, cefepime.

Table No. 10 Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of Gram-negative Bacteria

Antibiotics	<i>E. coli</i> (n=9)		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (n=6)		<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (n=4)		<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (n=3)		<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i> (n=3)		<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (n=2)	
	S (%)	R (%)	S (%)	R (%)	S(%)	R(%)	S (%)	R (%)	S (%)	R (%)	S (%)	R(%)
Amikacin	4(44.44)	5(55.56)	4(66.67)	2(33.33)	2(50)	2(50)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	1(50)	1(50)
Gentamicin	7(77.77)	2(22.23)	1(16.66)	5(83.34)	1(25)	3(75)	0(0)	3(100)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	1(50)	1(50)
Ciprofloxacin	3(33.34)	6(66.66)	2(33.33)	4(66.67)	1(25)	3(75)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	1(50)	1(50)
Cefotaxime	2(22.23)	7(77.77)	1(16.66)	5(83.34)	0(0)	4(100)	0(0)	3(100)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	1(50)	1(50)
Imipenem	2(22.23)	7(77.77)	2(33.33)	4(66.67)	1(25)	3(75)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	0(0)	2(100)
Cefoxitin	3(33.34)	6(66.66)	1(16.66)	5(83.34)	2(50)	2(50)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	0(0)	3(100)	0(0)	2(100)
Ceftazidime	0(0)	9(100)	1(16.66)	5(83.34)	2(50)	2(50)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	0(0)	2(100)
Piperacillin-tazobactam	2(22.23)	7(77.77)	1(16.66)	5(83.34)	1(25)	3(75)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	1(50)	1(50)
Cefoperazone sulbactam	1(11.12)	8(88.88)	2(33.33)	4(66.67)	2(50)	2(50)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	1(50)	1(50)
Co-trimoxazole	3(33.34)	6(66.66)	2(33.33)	4(66.67)	2(50)	2(50)	3(100)	0(0)	1(33.34)	2(66.66)	2(100)	0(0)
Fosfomycin	7(77.77)	2(22.23)	5(83.34)	1(16.66)	2(50)	2(50)	3(100)	0(0)	2(66.66)	1(33.34)	2(100)	0(0)

Fig. No. 29 (A) Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of Gram-negative Bacteria

Fig. No. 29 (B) Antimicrobial Resistant Pattern of Gram-negative Isolates

Among the isolates from sterile body fluid, *Escherichia coli* was predominant in Gram negative bacteria. *Escherichia coli* showed maximum sensitivity to gentamicin, fosfomycin 7(77.78%) followed by amikacin 4(44.44%) and maximum resistance to

cefoperazone sulbactam 8(88.88%) followed by cefotaxime, imipenem and piperacillin, tazobactam 7(77.77%).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa showed maximum sensitivity to fosfomycin 5(83.34%) followed by amikacin 4(66.67) and maximum resistance to gentamicin, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, piperacillin tazobactam 5(83.34%) followed by ciprofloxacin, imipenem, cefoperazone sulbactam, co-trimoxazole 4(66.67%).

Klebsiella pneumoniae showed maximum sensitivity to amikacin, ceftazidime, cefoperazone sulbactam, co-trimoxazole, fosfomycin 2(50%) followed by gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, imipenem, piperacillin tazobactam 1(25%) and maximum resistance to cefotaxime 4(100%) followed by gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, imipenem, piperacillin tazobactam 3(75%).

Acinetobacter baumannii complex showed maximum sensitivity to co-trimoxazole, fosfomycin 3(100%) followed by imipenem ceftazidime 2(66.67%) and maximum resistance to gentamicin, cefotaxime 3(100%) followed by amikacin, ciprofloxacin, ceftazidime piperacillin tazobactam, cefoperazone sulbactam 2(66.66%).

Pseudomonas species shows maximum sensitivity to amikacin, ceftazidime, piperacillin tazobactam, fosfomycin 2(66.66%) and showed maximum resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, cefotaxime, imipenem, cefoperazone sulbactam, co-trimoxazole 2(66.66%). *Enterobacter cloacae complex* showed 100% sensitivity to co-trimoxazole and fosfomycin and showed 100% resistance to imipenem, ceftazidime.

Table No. 11 Prevalence of ESBL Producing Gram negative Bacteria

Bacterial isolates	ESBL Positive (%)	ESBL Negative(%)
<i>E. Coli</i>	5(55.56)	4(44.44)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2(33.33)	4(66.67)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1(25)	3(75)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii complex</i>	0 (0)	3(100)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae complex</i>	2(100)	0(0)
<i>Pseudomonas. spp.</i>	1(33)	2(67)

Fig. No. 30 Prevalence of ESBL Producing Gram negative Bacteria

Out of 27 Gram-negative bacterial isolates, *Escherichia coli* 5 (55.56%) were ESBL producers followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 2 (33.33%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 1 (25%), *Enterobacter cloacae complex* 2 (100%) and *Pseudomonas species* 1 (33). *Acinetobacter baumannii complex* was non ESBL producer. The total number of ESBL producers in our study was 11 (40.74%)

Table No. 12 Prevalence of MBL Producing Gram negative Bacteria

Bacterial isolates	MBL Positive (%)	MBL Negative (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	6 (66.67)	3 (33.33)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2 (33.33)	4 (66.67)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2 (50)	2 (50)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	2 (67)	1 (33)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	0 (0)	2 (100)
<i>Pseudomonas species</i>	1 (33)	2 (67)

Fig. No. 31 Prevalence of MBL Producing Gram negative Bacteria

Out of 27 Gram-negative bacterial isolates, *Escherichia coli*, 6 (66.67%) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 2 (33.33%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 2 (50%), *Pseudomonas species* 1 (33%) were MBL producers.

Enterobacter cloacae complex was non MBL producer. The total number of MBL producers in our study was 13 (48.15%)

Table No. 13 Prevalence of AmpC Producing Gram negative Bacteria

Bacterial isolates	AmpC Positive (%)	AmpC Negative (%)
<i>E. Coli</i>	0(0)	9(100)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2(33.33)	4(66.67)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2(50)	2(50)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii complex</i>	0(0)	3(100)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae complex</i>	0(0)	2(100)
<i>Pseudomonas species</i>	1(33)	2(67)

Fig. No. 32 Prevalence of AmpC Producing Gram negative Bacteria

Out of 27 Gram-negative bacterial isolates *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 2 (33.33%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 2 (50%) and *Pseudomonas species* 1 (33%) were AmpC producers. *Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter baumannii complex* and *Enterobacter cloacae complex* were non AmpC producers.

The total number of AmpC producers in our study was 5 (18.51%).

Table No. 14 Multidrug Resistance pattern of Bacterial isolates from Sterile body fluids

Bacterial isolates	RG0	RG1	RG2	RG3	RG4	≥RG5	MDR (RG3+RG4+≥RG5) (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	0	0	0	1	2	6	9 (28.12)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	0	0	0	1	1	4	6 (18.75)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	0	0	0	1	1	2	4 (12.5)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	0	0	1	0	2	0	2 (6.25)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	0	0	1	0	0	1	1 (3.13)
<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	0	0	0	1	0	2	3 (9.37)
Coagulase Positive <i>Staphylococcus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	3	3 (9.37)
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	1 (3.13)
<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	1 (3.13)
Total	0	0	2	5	6	19	30 (93.75)

Among the total 32 Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial isolates, 30 (93.75%) bacterial isolates were Multidrug resistance. Out of all Multidrug resistance organisms *E. coli* was high in percentage which is 28.12%. followed by *P. aeruginosa* 18.75% and *K. pneumoniae* 12.5%. And least were *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Enterococcus faecium* exhibited 3.13%.

DISCUSSION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines sterility as the condition of being free from the presence of viable microorganisms.¹⁶⁵ When humans are born, they acquire a diverse array of microorganisms, encompassing bacteria, viruses, fungi, protozoa and helminths.^{165,166,167,168} Humans and microbes coexist in a symbiotic relationship, contributing to host physiology, the development of the immune system, metabolism and various other essential functions.^{165,166,169,170} This collective assembly of microbes associated with humans is commonly referred to as the “microbiota”.^{166,171}

However, certain organs or tissues in our body were traditionally believed to be sterile, including blood, cerebrospinal fluid, pleural fluid, peritoneal fluid, pericardial fluid, bone, synovial fluid, lymph nodes, brain, heart, liver, spleen, vitreous fluid, kidney, pancreas, ovary, and vascular tissue.^{165,172} Because these sites and fluids are biological fluids that typically do not harbor microorganisms as commensals when in a healthy state.^{1,3,161}

The detection and identification of microorganism in sterile body fluids in early stage is crucial step for appropriate management of infectious diseases.^{6, 173} Invasion of different types of microorganisms in sterile parts of the body can cause systemic illness.⁹

Even though any microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, or parasites can be isolated from these sites, it is considered pathogenic and can be life-threatening to patients who are critical in conditions specially those admitted to intensive care and high dependency units of the hospitals.^{2,174,175}

In the present study, samples were received from all the age groups, their age ranged from new-born baby to 85-year-old. Majority of them were from 41 to 60 year age group and 74.45% were males and 25.55% were females. These findings were largely consistent with those reported by Waske et al.¹⁷⁶ in which 79% were males, while 21% were females, Perween et al.¹⁷⁷ showed 63.6% males and 36.4% females and in study by Shrestha et al.⁴ 54% were male while 46% were female.

In this study, the overall prevalence of bacterial pathogens was 17.77%. This finding is comparable with previous studies from India, Telangana 20.55% Durga et al.¹⁷³, Ujjain

Madhya Pradesh 21.1% Waske et al.¹⁷⁶, Hubli, Karnataka 22% Harshika et al.² Eastern Ethiopia 17% Shume et al.⁹ and Northern Ethiopia 20.2% Tsegay et al.³ Lower prevalence rate were observed from studies like Northwest Ethiopia 7.5% Admas et al.¹⁷⁸, Balikesir, Turkey 9.7% Duran et al.¹⁷⁹ And in India, Uttar Pradesh 9.69% Singh et al.¹⁷⁵ Higher prevalence rate was observed from studies in Northern India, 31.13% Kar et al.⁸, in Nepal, Dharan, Sunsari 31% Shrestha et al.⁴, again in India, New Delhi 30% Sharma et al.⁵, in South India, 29.9% Madigubba et al.¹⁶¹, and in Bhubaneswar, Odisha 28% Tiwari et al.¹⁷⁴ These variations can be attributed to differences in sample processing methods, seasonal variation, and infection control practices across different regions and studies.

Table No. 15 Comparative study showing prevalence of bacterial growth.

Author	Year	Prevalence (%)
Kar et al. ⁸	2019-2020	31.13%
Shrestha et al. ⁴	2012-2016	31%
Sharma et al. ⁵	2015	30%
Madigubba et al. ¹⁶¹	2017-2019	29.9%
Tiwari et al. ¹⁷⁴	2022	28%
Harshika et al. ²	2017	22%
Waske et al. ¹⁷⁶	2021	21.1%
Durga et al. ¹⁷³	2013-2017	20.55%
Tsegay et al. ³	2013-2017	20.2%
Shume et al. ⁹	2021	17%
Singh et al. ¹⁷⁵	2023	9.69%
Duran et al. ¹⁷⁹	2017-2020	9.7%
Admas et al. ¹⁷⁸	2022	7.5%
Present study	2021-2023	17.77%

In our study, 84% of infections were caused by Gram-negative bacteria, while 16% were attributed to Gram-positive bacteria. Similar findings were observed in the study by Madigubba et al.¹⁶¹ where 83.2% were Gram negative bacteria and 16.3% were Gram-positive bacteria. This predominance of Gram-negative bacteria has also been

noted in other studies, such as those by Sharma et al.⁵ (90% Gram-negative and 9% Gram-positive bacteria) and Sultana et al.⁶ (72.7% Gram-negative and 27.3% Gram-positive bacteria). Gram-negative bacteria showed a higher prevalence rate in sterile body fluids due to their durable outer membrane, which resists antibiotics and immune defenses, as well as their capacity to form biofilms and produce potent toxins that increase their virulence.

Conversely, some studies in Ethiopia have shown a predominance of Gram-positive bacterial infections, with 52.3% Gram-positive bacteria compared to 47.7% Gram-negative bacteria Ephrem Tsegay et al.³ Studies conducted in India and the USA, such as those by Vishalakshi et al.¹⁸⁰ and Bourbeau et al.¹⁸¹ which also reported a predominance of Gram-positive bacterial infections.

In our study, among total samples, 29.45% were pleural fluid, 27.78% ascitic fluid, 26.67% CSF, 12.78% peritoneal fluid. Among 32 positive growth, *E. coli* was the most common isolated organism constituted 28.12% followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18.75% and in Gram positive bacteria *coagulase positive Staphylococcus* was in majority 9.37%. Similar results were obtained by Rouf et al.¹, Harshika et al.², Shrestha et al.⁴, Sharma et al.⁵, Sultana et al.⁶, and Durga et al.¹⁷³ *E. coli* is the most common disease-causing bacteria in sterile body fluids according to the isolation rate of findings of all these studies.

Comparative study of Distribution of antimicrobial susceptibility testing –

Gram positive organisms:

In the present study, bacterial isolates were tested against various antimicrobial agents, and their susceptibility patterns were observed.

Gram-positive organisms constituted about 16% of the total isolates in our study. Among these, coagulase-positive *Staphylococcus* was the most prevalent, demonstrating 100% susceptibility to vancomycin and 66.67% susceptibility to tetracycline. These results align with those of Singh et al.¹⁷⁵ who reported 100% susceptibility to vancomycin and 50% to tetracycline. Similarly, Waske et al.¹⁷⁶ found 100% susceptibility to vancomycin and 50% to tetracycline, Rouf et al.¹ observed 100% susceptibility to vancomycin, Harshika et al.² noted 100% susceptibility to vancomycin, and Tiwari et al.¹⁷⁴ also reported 100% susceptibility to vancomycin.

100% resistance was observed to ciprofloxacin, ceftazidime, erythromycin, cefepime, levofloxacin, and ampicillin. This is similar to findings by Sultana et al.⁶ where 100% resistance to ampicillin was reported and by Tsegay et al.³ who observed 78.6% resistance to ampicillin.

Streptococcus pneumoniae showed 100% susceptibility to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, clindamycin, vancomycin, amikacin, cefepime, levofloxacin, and linezolid. This is consistent with findings by Durga et al.¹⁷³ who reported 100% susceptibility to clindamycin and vancomycin, and 70% susceptibility to amikacin as well as Tsegay et al.³ who observed 100% susceptibility to ciprofloxacin.

Streptococcus pneumoniae showed 100% resistance to tetracycline, ceftazidime, cotrimoxazole, erythromycin, and ampicillin. This finding is similar to the study by Adams et al.¹⁷⁸ which reported 100% resistance to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (cotrimoxazole).

Enterococcus faecium showed 100% susceptibility to clindamycin, vancomycin, cotrimoxazole, erythromycin, levofloxacin, linezolid, and ampicillin. This is similar to findings by Kasana et al.¹⁸² who reported 100% susceptibility to linezolid and vancomycin, and Madigubba et al.¹⁶¹ who observed 99.9% susceptibility to linezolid and 89.9% to vancomycin.

Enterococcus faecium exhibited complete resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, ceftazidime, amikacin, and cefepime. These findings are consistent with those of Tsegay et al.³ who also observed 100% resistance to ciprofloxacin.

Gram Negative organisms:

Gram-negative organisms constituted about 84% of the total isolates, with *E. coli* being the most common pathogen among them.

E. coli showed maximum susceptibility to both gentamicin and fosfomycin at 77.78% followed by amikacin at 44.44%. These findings can be correlated with the study by Durga et al.¹⁷³ which reported 85% susceptibility to amikacin and 75% to gentamicin as well as Madigubba et al.¹⁶¹ which found 83% susceptibility to amikacin. Additionally, the study by Rouf et al.¹ indicated that gentamicin and amikacin were the most effective antibiotics against *E. coli*.

E. coli showed maximum resistance to cefoperazone-sulbactam at 88.88%, followed by cefotaxime, imipenem, and piperacillin-tazobactam at 77.77%. These findings are similar to those of Kasana et al.¹⁸² who reported 73.7% resistance to cefotaxime and 44.1% to piperacillin-tazobactam; Madigubba et al.¹⁶¹ who observed 62.7% resistance to cefoperazone-sulbactam; and Sheikhabaei et al.¹⁸³ who found high resistance rates to both piperacillin-tazobactam and cefoperazone-sulbactam.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa demonstrated the highest sensitivity to fosfomycin at 83.34%, followed by amikacin at 66.67%. These findings align with those of Durga et al.¹⁷³ and Shume et al.²⁰⁹, who reported 75% sensitivity to amikacin, and Madigubba et al.¹⁶¹ who observed 59.6% sensitivity to amikacin.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa exhibited maximum resistance to gentamicin, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, and piperacillin-tazobactam (83.34%), followed by ciprofloxacin, imipenem, cefoperazone-sulbactam, and co-trimoxazole (66.67%). Our findings are similar to those of Kasana et al.¹⁸² who reported 86.2% resistance to cefoperazone-sulbactam.

Klebsiella pneumoniae demonstrated 50% sensitivity to amikacin, ceftazidime, cefoperazone-sulbactam, co-trimoxazole, and fosfomycin. These results are comparable to those of Shume et al.⁹ who found 75% sensitivity to amikacin. Furthermore, all *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates were sensitive only to reserved antibiotics such as tigecycline and colistin, as reported by Waske et al.¹⁷⁶

Klebsiella pneumoniae exhibited 100% resistance to cefotaxime, followed by 75% resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, imipenem, and piperacillin-tazobactam. According to Sultana et al.⁶ resistance to cefotaxime was reported at 60%.

Acinetobacter baumannii complex showed 100% sensitivity to co-trimoxazole and fosfomycin, followed by 66.67% sensitivity to imipenem and ceftazidime. Durga et al.¹⁷³ found 70% sensitivity to imipenem.

Acinetobacter baumannii complex showed 100% resistance to gentamicin and cefotaxime, followed by 66.66% resistance to amikacin, ciprofloxacin, piperacillin-tazobactam, and cefoperazone-sulbactam. Our study indicates that *Acinetobacter* is one of the most resistant pathogens to many antibiotics, consistent with findings by Sharma et al.⁵ and Rouf et al.¹ who also reported high resistance in *Acinetobacter baumannii*

complex. Furthermore, studies by Kempf et al.¹⁸⁴ and Karagkou et al.¹⁸⁵ highlight *Acinetobacter* as a significant public health concern, particularly regarding antimicrobial therapy and the need for life support.

Enterobacter cloacae complex showed 100% sensitivity to co-trimoxazole and fosfomycin, and 100% resistance to imipenem, ceftazidime, and ceftaxime. However, cefotaxime exhibited 50% sensitivity and 50% resistance, which is comparable to the findings of Harshika et al.² where all antibiotics were 100% sensitive except for cefotaxime, which showed 100% resistance.

According to Sodani et al.¹⁸⁶ body fluids can be susceptible to infections caused by both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Therefore, ongoing monitoring and surveillance of organisms responsible for these infections are essential for developing effective infection control policies. This approach helps clinicians in selecting appropriate antibiotics.

Increasing patient awareness about the dangers of antibiotic misuse and overuse is crucial. Encouraging empirical treatment and establishing hospital-based antibiotic policies specific to sterile body fluids are necessary steps. These policies assist physicians in delivering timely and effective treatment, ultimately reducing mortality and morbidity rates significantly, as emphasized by Tiwari et al.¹⁷⁴

To effectively control the spread of antibiotic resistance, it is crucial to implement strong antibiotic stewardship programs. These programs play a vital role in ensuring judicious use of antibiotics, thereby preserving their effectiveness in treating infections.

Comparative analysis of Phenotypes among Body Fluid Isolates:

In present study, ESBL producers were found to be 40.74%. Similarly, Shrestha et al.⁴ reported 37% and Singh et al.¹⁷⁵ 25% of ESBL producers. Our findings were almost comparable with that of Shrestha et al. but on a higher side compared to Singh et al.

In the present study, MBL was detected in 48.15% of cases. Kamble et al.¹⁸⁷ reported 4.2% MBL producers in different fluids, and no ESBL and MBL producers in CSF. In the present study one out of two isolates from CSF was either ESBL or MBL positive. The presence of ESBL and MBL isolates in the CSF in the present study indicates the development of resistant strains. Out 27 Gram negative isolates 5 (18.51 %) were

AmpC positive. More prevalence of these resistant phenotypes in the present study might be attributed to increased use of Beta- Lactam Antimicrobials in therapeutic management.

The rising prevalence of AmpC, MBL, and ESBL producing isolates signals a concerning trend of increasing resistance mechanisms among bacteria, which could render existing antimicrobial therapies less effective.¹⁸⁸

SUMMARY

- The present study, titled "Bacterial Isolates and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern in Body Fluids of Patients from a Tertiary Care Hospital," was conducted in the Department of Microbiology at Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences, Krishna Hospital and Medical Research Centre, Karad.
- A total of 180 different sterile body fluids were collected for culture during the study period. Out of these, 32 samples (17.77%) were culture-positive, while the remaining 148 samples (82.23%) were sterile.
- The majority of both male and female patients were from the 41 to 60 age group, with 48 males (26.67%) and 15 females (8.33%).
- Out of 180 samples, 134 (74.45%) were from male patients and 46 (25.55%) from female patients.
- The majority of patients were from the Medicine ICU, accounting for 83 (46.12%) of the cases, while the least number were from the OBGY department, with only 2 (1.11%) cases.
- Pleural fluid was the most common sample, with 53 cases (29.45%), while bile and synovial fluid were the least common, each with 1 case (0.55%).
- Among the culture-positive samples, the frequency of Gram-negative bacteria was high with 27 out of 32 (84%) and Gram-positive bacteria were 5 out of 32 (16%).
- Among Gram-positive bacteria, coagulase-positive *Staphylococcus* was the most frequently isolated with 3 (9.37%), followed by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Enterococcus faecium*, each with 1 (3.13%).
- Among Gram-negative bacteria, *E. coli* was the most frequently isolated with 9 (28.12%), followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with 6 (18.75%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* with 4 (12.5%), *Acinetobacter baumannii complex* with 3 (9.37%), and *Enterobacter cloacae complex* with 2 (6.25%).

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- *Coagulase-positive Staphylococcus* showed 100% resistance to ciprofloxacin, ceftazidime. 100% sensitivity was seen to vancomycin and maximum sensitivity to tetracycline 66.67%. *Coagulase positive staphylococcus* demonstrated 100% positivity for MRSA.
 - *Streptococcus pneumoniae* showed 100% resistance to tetracycline, ceftazidime. 100% sensitivity was seen to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin.
 - *Enterococcus faecium* showed 100% resistance to gentamicin. 100% sensitivity was seen to tetracycline, clindamycin.
 - *E. coli* showed maximum resistance to ceftazidime-sulbactam (88.88%), followed by imipenem (77.77%). maximum sensitivity was seen to gentamicin, fosfomycin 7(77.78%)
 - *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed maximum resistance to gentamicin, ceftazidime, (83.34%). Maximum sensitivity was seen to gentamicin, fosfomycin 77.78%
 - *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed 100% resistance to ceftazidime, followed by gentamicin (75%). 50% sensitivity was seen to amikacin, fosfomycin.
 - *Acinetobacter baumannii complex* showed maximum resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin (66.66%). 100% sensitivity was seen to co-trimoxazole, fosfomycin.
 - *Enterobacter cloacae complex* showed 100% resistance to imipenem, ceftazidime. 100% sensitivity was seen to co-trimoxazole and fosfomycin.
 - The prevalence of Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase was 40.74%.
 - The occurrence rate of Metallo Beta-Lactamase (MBL) was 48.15%.
 - AmpC Beta lactamase was found in 18.51%. of isolates.

CONCLUSION

The present study emphasized the burden of bacterial infection in sterile body fluids among patients at our hospital. Determining antibiotic susceptibility patterns and screening for ESBL, MBL, and AmpC among isolates are crucial for effective infection control. Based on our findings, it is imperative for microbiologists to not only identify the causative organisms but also to inform clinicians about latest resistance pattern.

In this study, we aim to highlight that Gram-negative organism, particularly *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, are the most common causes of sterile body fluid infections in our institution and show sensitivity to gentamicin and fosfomycin. This suggests these drugs may be effective treatment options.

Antibiotic therapy must be chosen with great caution, and it is important to continually assess the sensitivity-resistance patterns of the isolates. Given the changing bacterial resistance in the hospital and the population of western Maharashtra, this study might help in formulating an antibiotic policy for our institute.

Knowledge of the bacteriological profile is essential for clinicians to administer appropriate empirical therapy. Understanding antimicrobial sensitivities enables the judicious use of medications, thereby helping to prevent the development of drug resistance.

Infections affecting sterile body fluids are critical due to their high mortality and morbidity rates. Timely identification of the causative organisms and their antibiotic susceptibility is pivotal. Prompt initiation of appropriate antibiotic therapy can shorten hospital stays and mitigate the emergence of drug resistance, making early diagnosis and treatment essential in clinical management strategies.

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PROFORMA

- **Name:**
- **Age:**
- **Sex:**
- **IPD/ Number:**
- **Ward Number:**
- **Underlying Number:**
- **Duration of Hospitalization:**
- **Laboratory details:**
- **Sample:**
- **Gram stain:**
- **Culture:**
- **Colony characteristics:**
- **Identification of the organism:**
- **Antibiotic susceptibility test:**
 - **Antibiogram:**
 - **MRSA:**
 - **VRE:**
 - **ESBL:**
 - **MBL:**
 - **AmpC:**

INFORMED CONSENT FORM IN ENGLISH

Protocol No:

- Title of study: Study of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in body fluids from a tertiary care hospital.
- Name of Participant: -
- Name of Principal Investigator: Rounak S. Patel
- Name of Department: Medical Microbiology

I, -----have read the information or the information has been read to me. The nature of study, possible risk and benefits to me, precautions to be taken by me, my rights and responsibilities related to this study are explained to me by the investigator to my satisfaction. I have understood that the information/data obtained from this study may be used for scientific purpose (Publication/presentation in scientific meetings) by the investigators, without revealing my identity. I have no objection for this.

I have understood that I can withdraw from this study at any point of time without giving any reason and this will not affect my future treatment in this hospital. I have understood whom to contact in case of any adverse effect/doubt

I am also aware that the investigator can terminate my participation in this study at any time due to any reason, without taking my consent

1. I hereby give my consent to participate in the study titled “:

Study of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in body fluids of patients from a tertiary care hospital.

- Signature/left thumb impression of participant
- Name & Signature/left thumb impression of legal guardian/parent (if participant is incompetent/child below 18 years
- Signature & Name of impartial witness (In case of participant/legal guardian is illiterate person)

contact No:

- If child participant-
- Child Assent taken -Yes/No
- Name & signature of Investigator/Co-investigator

INFORMED CONSENT FORM IN MARATHI

संमतीपत्र

शिर्षक : तृतीयक केअर हॉस्पिटलमधून बॅक्टेरियाच्या पृथक्करण आणि शरीरातील द्रवपदार्थांच्या प्रतिजैविक संवेदनाक्षमतेचा अभ्यास.

भाग घेणाऱ्यांचे नावं-

प्रमुख तपासणी अधिकाऱ्यांचे नावं - रौनक श. पटेल

मार्गदर्शक नावं - डॉ. स. के. पवार

विभागाचे नावं- सूक्ष्मजीवशास्त्र

मी श्री/श्रीमती/सौ वय वर्षे असे लिहून देतो की / देते की मला संशोधकाने त्यांच्या संशोधनाबद्दल संपूर्ण माहिती दिली असून माझ्या सर्व प्रश्नांची योग्य अचूक व समाधानकारक उत्तरे मला त्यांनी दिली आहेत.

या संशोधनातून मिळालेल्या माहितीचा उपयोग संशोधकीय उपक्रमासाठी घेण्याची शक्यता आहे. या संशोधनातून मी माझा सहभाग माझ्या मर्जीनुसार केव्हाही काढू शकतो/शकते. अशी कल्पना संशोधकांनी मला दिली आहे. माझी काही शंका असेल तर कोणाशी संपर्क साधायचा हे मला माहित आहे.

तसेच संशोधक मला कोणती ही पूर्व सूचना न देता या संशोधनातून बाजूला करू शकतात याची कल्पना दिली आहे.

मी असे लिहून देतो की / देते की वरील संशोधन संदर्भात माझे जे काही प्रश्न अथवा शंका असतील त्या मी केव्हाही विचारू शकतो/शकते याची मला खात्री झाली आहे.

सबब सदरचे संशोधन प्रकल्पाचे नावं -

तृतीयक केअर हॉस्पिटलमधून बॅक्टेरियाच्या पृथक्करण आणि शरीरातील द्रवपदार्थांच्या प्रतिजैविक संवेदनाक्षमतेचा अभ्यास.

असे असून त्याबद्दलची संपूर्ण माहिती मला मिळाल्यामुळे सदर प्रतिज्ञा पत्र मी माझे खुशीने देत आहे.

1) भाग घेणाऱ्यांचे नावं -

मोबाइल नंबर

सही

दिनांक

2) साक्षीदारचे नावं -

मोबाइल नंबर

सही

दिनांक

ETHICAL CERTIFICATE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICS COMMITTEE KRISHNA INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES "DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY", KARAD.

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Karad, Dist. Satara (Maharashtra State) Pin : 415 539
Tel : 02164 - 241555-8 Fax : 02164 - 243272 / 242170
Website : www.kimskarad.in E-mail : iec@klmskarad.in

Ref. No. KIMSDU/IEC/04/2022

Date: 09/05/2022

CERTIFICATE

The Institutional Ethics Committee has hereby given permission to initiate the research project (Protocol Number 069/2021-2022) titled, "STUDY OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES AND ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN IN BODY FLUIDS OF PATIENTS FROM A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL" by Mr. Rounak Shakil Patel under the guidance of Dr. Satyajeet K. Pawar, Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences, Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences "Deemed To Be University", Karad.

Dr. Mrs. V. M. Thorat
Member Secretary
Institutional Ethics Committee
Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences
"Deemed To Be University", Karad

PLAGIARISM CERTIFICATE

KRISHNA VISHWA VIDYAPEETH (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) KARAD
DIRECTORATE OF RESEARCH
Plagiarism Verification Certificate

1. **Name of Student:** Rounak Patel
2. **Registration Number:** MS - 2021004
3. **Title of the thesis:** "Study of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in body fluids of patients from a tertiary care hospital"
4. **Department:** Microbiology
5. **Name of Guide and Designation:** Dr. S. K. Pawar, Associate Professor, Dept. of Microbiology, KIMS
6. **Name of Co-guide and Designation:** NA

7. The above thesis was verified for similarity detection. The report is as follows:

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I/C Director of Research,
Krishna Vishwa Vidyapeeth, Karad

